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Associated project to RESILIENCE

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1. Document Overview

The Ministero dell’Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE)¹ for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality, and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

Within the structure of the ITSERR project, the Work Package 8 (WP8)—*uBIQUity*, whose title incorporates the “BI” of the Bible(s) and the “QU” of the Qur’ān, investigates the sacred texts of Christianity and Islam across diverse environments and historical periods, using both traditional and computational methods. This analysis is carried out through two extensive *corpora*: Greek and Latin Christian commentaries—broadly understood as written forms of exegesis—on the Bible(s), composed from the patristic era to the late Byzantine period; and classical commentaries on the Qur’ān written in Arabic (*tafāsīr*), dating from the rise of Islam to the 15th century. It is widely acknowledged that no text emerges in isolation, and that every text is inevitably shaped by the written (and oral) culture of its author(s). This is particularly evident in the case of ancient commentaries. Indeed, these exegetical works are intrinsically intertextual: they were composed specifically to explain and interpret, step by step, the sacred texts, and constitute a literary genre—whether Greek and Latin biblical commentaries or *tafāsīr*—that develops cumulatively, drawing on and juxtaposing different sources in relation to a given verse or passage. In this sense, the intertextual references embedded in ancient commentaries form their (in)visible framework—or, we might even say, their backbone. Whether employed consciously or unconsciously, they function as “places of memory,” making the sacred texts “ubiquitous”—hence the title of the project.

By integrating research methods from the humanities with state-of-the-art computer science, *uBIQUity* is developing a novel research tool capable of identifying biblical references, Qur’ānic quotations, and reuses of canonical and non-canonical collections of the Sayings of the Prophet (*’ahādīth*) in ancient and medieval Christian and Islamic works with a higher degree of accuracy than existing resources².

¹ ITSERR is a consortium composed of National Research Council (CNR), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE), University of Naples L’Orientale (UNIOR), University of Palermo (UNIPA), and University of Torino (UNITO).

² For an in-depth scholarly overview and methodological reflection on intertextuality in relation to the Bible(s), along with a critical discussion of the digital tools currently available for detecting textual similarities, see A. Mambelli and M. Costa, *Exploring the uBIQUity of Biblical Texts: Tradition and Innovation in the Ancient and Digital Worlds*, in A. Melloni and F. Cadeddu (eds.), *The Digital Turn in Religious Studies. Research, Services, Infrastructures*, Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2025, pp. 149-176; D. Dainese, L. Bigoni, and M. Zanella, *Resilient Septuagint Between Borges and Asimov: A State-of-the-Art Case of uBIQUity*, in Melloni and Cadeddu (eds.), *The Digital Turn*, pp. 177-206; D. Dainese and A. Mambelli, *Intertestualità tra Bibbie e antichi commentari cristiani: l’esempio di simul nel De Genesi ad litteram di Agostino*, in “Lexicon Philosophicum: International Journal for the History of Texts and Ideas”, 11 (2023–2024), pp. 39-65: <https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/article/view/872/726>.

The WP8 team members are:

- Sara **ABRAM**, University of Palermo (UNIPA): Arabic texts.
- Marcello **COSTA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Fabrizio **D’AVENIA**, WP8 Leader, UNIPA.
- Cinzia **FERRARA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Anna **MAMBELLI**, WP8 Scientific Coordinator and Product Owner, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE): Greek and Latin texts.
- Chiara **PALILLO**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Fabio **TUTRONE**, UNIPA: Latin texts.

Regarding research in the field of computer science, for the Latin section, the collaboration with the UNIMORE team composed of Davide **CAFFAGNI**, Federico **COCCHI**, Marcella **CORNIA**, Rita **CUCCHIARA**, and also with Cesare **CONCORDIA** and Carlo **MEGHINI** of the National Research Council (CNR, Pisa) is fundamental. As for the Arabic section of WP8, Giovanni **PUC CETTI** of the CNR is working on the IT side.

Concerning research and work on Ancient Greek, WP8 has decided to collaborate with the team of another project with similar aims, which has been incubated in the framework of RESILIENCE RI, namely the PRIN (Italian Research Project of National Interest, n. 20229E83B3) *Resilient Septuagint. An Initial Exploration of the Semantics of Killing and Healing in the Septuagint and its Reception in Patristic and Late Antique Sources (3rd cent. BCE-5th cent. CE)*. This PRIN project involves the *Alma Mater Studiorum* University of Bologna (UNIBO, PI Research Unit), the University of Bari (UNIBA), and the University of Catania (UNICT). The *Resilient Septuagint* team members are: Luca **ARCARI** (University of Naples Federico II), Laura **BIGONI** (UNIBO), Laura **CARNEVALE** (UNIBA Research Unit Chief), Davide **DAINESE** (Principal Investigator [PI], UNIBO), Isabella **PIGNOCCO** (UNICT-UNIBO), Arianna **ROTONDO** (UNICT Research Unit Chief and deputy PI), Giorgia **SAMPÒ** (DDC University of Southern Denmark-UNIBO), Gianluca **SCATIGNO** (UNIBO), and Marco **ZANELLA** (University of Padua-UNIBO). This collaboration between WP8 and *Resilient Septuagint* has included and will continue to include the development of a shared methodological framework and interoperable datasets for the study of Greek biblical texts and their heritage.

This document is the **fourth deliverable from the WP8 of ITSERR (D8.2)** and presents **the team’s work on improving the usability and accessibility of the *uBIQUity* platform for its target audience. The work followed two main directions: 1. testing the user experience of the platform’s interface, and 2. developing comprehensive training materials. These materials describe the sources included in the tool, their relevance, available search functionalities, and technical aspects related to the dataset structure and the underlying algorithm, as well as a tutorial guiding users through the practical use of the platform.**

The first part of the document reports on the results of a qualitative test conducted on the *uBIQUity* prototype in collaboration with UNGUESS, a company specialized in user experience evaluation and crowdtesting.³ The objective of the test was to validate the prototype’s design, usability, and responsiveness, based on feedback from five end users, i.e. scholars in the fields of the humanities and the history of religions. The feedback collected during this interview-based test was examined and discussed by the WP8 team and has already been taken into account, with some elements implemented in the *Alpha* version of the *uBIQUity* tool. This whitepaper categorizes the results into positive elements, minor and major issues, and user needs, providing a detailed analysis of the users’ experience with key features such as browsing, searching, result visualization (nodes, variants, columns), and saving/exporting workflows. Overall, the test aimed to refine the platform before its final development by identifying both its strengths and areas requiring clarification or improvement.

The second part of the whitepaper presents the training material developed for users of the *uBIQUity* platform. The course, titled “**Training on *uBIQUity*: The Legacy of Sacred Texts. Exploring Intertextuality Between the Ancient and Digital Worlds**”, introduces participants to the reception and reuse of the sacred texts of Christianity in Greek and Latin Christian literature (from the Patristic to the Byzantine period), and to the reuse of the Qur’ān and the *Sunna* in classical Arabic Qur’ānic commentaries (*tafāsīr*) up to the 15th century. Developed by the *uBIQUity* team, the training combines traditional philology, historical contextualization, and exegetical methods with digital tools and AI-driven techniques. Participants first gain an overview of the Ancient Greek, Latin, and Arabic *corpora* and their exegetical traditions; they then explore how intertextuality is defined, classified, and annotated across biblical-patristic and Islamic contexts, including the creation of structured datasets and metadata. In the subsequent digital section, participants engage with hands-on modules that introduce the functioning of the *uBIQUity* retrieval system, search strategies (language-agnostic, language-aware, and semantic), and visualization tools for close and distant reading. A detailed tutorial guides participants through the main functionalities of the platform, from conducting searches to managing results, annotations, and notes. By combining traditional philological, historical, and exegetical methods with AI-driven digital tools, the course is intended for a broad audience, ranging from students and doctoral candidates to established scholars, and provides participants with the theoretical and practical skills to detect, analyze, and visualize intertextual relationships in ancient and medieval texts through an interdisciplinary approach. Training materials will be delivered through lectures, workshops, and multimedia resources available on the ITSERR platform, while this deliverable presents their written and synthetic version.

³ <https://unguess.io/it/>

2. *uBIQUity* Prototype Test and Evaluation

2.1. Test Objectives

The test aims to conduct a qualitative assessment to validate the design, usability, and responsiveness of the *uBIQUity* prototype to user needs. Its primary goal is to verify how effectively the platform supports researchers in exploring intertextual relationships and navigating complex textual data. A high-fidelity version of the prototype is provided at all stages of the evaluation, allowing participants to interact with its main features in realistic research scenarios. The feedback collected throughout the process helps identify strengths and weaknesses, guiding subsequent design iterations and ensuring continuous improvement prior to the final release.

2.2. Methodology

The methodology adopted was the **Moderate Prototype Test**, a qualitative evaluation method. In this approach, the study is overseen by a facilitator who interacts directly with participants. The moderator provides structured guidance, clarifies instructions, and addresses questions in real time as tasks are performed. This ensures both the continuity of the testing process and the reliability of the qualitative insights gathered.

In the context of *uBIQUity*, this approach was carried out by the ITSERR design partner UNGUESS. It consisted in testing the platform's interface prototype with real users who had no prior knowledge of the tool, in order to ensure unbiased and genuine reactions to its features and usability. The goal was to gather feedback and identify potential issues related to usability, functionality, and user experience before the final development phase.

The findings were classified into different categories to evaluate their impact:

- **Positive Elements:** Features or processes particularly appreciated by users.
- **Minor Issues:** Problems that may cause delays or frustration in task completion.
- **Major Issues:** Problems that significantly hinder or prevent task completion.
- **User Needs:** Requirements expressed by users regarding specific features or information.

As suggested by Jakob Nielsen and Thomas K. Landauer (1993),⁴ five end users were involved in the prototype test, as this number is generally sufficient to capture the main usability issues. All participants shared a strong interest in intertextuality and digital humanities, and their diverse

⁴ J. Nielsen, T.K. Landauer, *A Mathematical Model of the Finding of Usability Problems*, in *Proceedings of the INTERACT '93 and CHI '93 Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 24-29 April 1993)*, 1993, pp. 206-213: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/epdf/10.1145/169059.169166>; J. Nielsen, *Why You Only Need to Test with 5 Users*, in "Nielsen Norman Group", March 18, 2000: <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/why-you-only-need-to-test-with-5-users/>

academic backgrounds provided the WP8 team with complementary insights and cross-disciplinary perspectives.

2.3. Description of the Prototype Interface Features

As detailed in D8.1.2 – *Whitepaper on uBIQUity*, the *uBIQUity* tool was conceived as a platform designed to support intertextual analysis by integrating philological methods with computational techniques. That earlier document defined the tool’s overall objectives and described its main functionalities. The high-fidelity interactive prototype used for user testing was developed in close collaboration with end users, ensuring that the design reflected real research practices and needs. During the testing sessions, participants were asked to evaluate a series of key functionalities, structured around three main use cases and their related features:

Use Case 1 – Phrase research

- Comparison criteria and search filters
- Similarity Score and match results
- Results list and
 - *Ratings* functionality
 - *Search* feature
 - *Note* feature
 - *Source* feature
- Comparison
- Node Visualization
- Variant Graph
- Column (parallel) view
- Heat map
- Save flow and flows
- Note taking

Use Case 2 – Search by word

- Results view
- Results line graph
- Results map
- Results dictionary
- Export functionality

Use Case 3 – Browsing the corpus

- Navigation of the corpus
- Searching the corpus

The following sections summarize the most appreciated features identified during the testing phase, along with users' main requirements and overall evaluations.

2.3.1 Most Appreciated Features

- **Tool Startup & Intuitive Interface:** Users found the tool easy to start, thanks to a clear landing interface. Language selection (Arabic, Ancient Greek, Latin) was immediate and easy to understand. Both direct text input and corpus browsing were intuitive.
- **Comparison Criteria & Search Filters:** Considered helpful for users' tasks. The explanations provided for the comparison criteria were appreciated and easily accessible. The "Structures" icon was deemed self-explanatory, with 4 out of 5 users recognizing the reference to Artificial Intelligence.
- **Match Result Visualization:** Highly appreciated. In the column of results that appears on the right-hand side, references to individual passages matching the searched text (e.g., G_LXX Genesis 1:5) were clearly displayed. Bolded references helped highlight matches, and the distinction between quotations and apparatus in the list of results was easily noticeable. The results were understood to be sorted by relevance. Users understand that the results are ranked according to the degree of correspondence with the input text, aided by the explicit indication of how many words from the searched text appear identically in each result (i.e. 10/17).
- **Annotation Feature (Notes):** The icon was clear and intuitive for adding new notes. Zotero integration was understood, and retrieving past notes was straightforward. Users found the ability to annotate to be more personal and useful for their work.
- **Ease of Comparing Results:** The interface clearly communicated how to compare selected results (e.g., using the "Compare selected" checkbox).
- **Node Visualization:** Users found it useful and intuitive. The vertical column structure helped differentiate text from apparatus. It was clear to users how to show or hide the apparatus and how many results were being compared. The navigator was also recognized as useful.
- **Column View:** This more traditional view was appreciated for its clarity and contextualization, particularly for its clear distinction between text and apparatus and for highlighting matched segments.
- **Heat Map:** Despite readability issues, users valued the ability to explore occurrence distribution and density, making it a useful tool for quantitative analysis and distant reading.
- **Save Flow & Flows:** The "Save Flow" functionality was especially appreciated, with users easily identifying the entry point. They expected to be able to revisit their saved flows.
- **Single Word Search:** Starting a search for a single word was perceived as immediate and clear. The total occurrence count was visible and easily understood.
- **Line Graph:** Users considered it to be a useful and effective tool, particularly for visualizing citation density over time, and suitable for educational purposes.

- **Map:** It was deemed intuitive and appreciated for its visual impact in conveying the geographical distribution of texts or authors, particularly in more recent contexts.
- **Dictionary:** This feature was highly requested and widely appreciated. Users valued receiving lexical explanations directly within the platform and recognized the benefits of its integration with external sources.
- **Export Functionality:** The ability to export in research-relevant formats (PDF for reading/archive, DOC for editing) was appreciated.
- **Intuitive Navigation Experience:** The tool was found to be intuitive and easy to navigate without instructions. The interface was considered functional, with appreciated organizational clarity. Overall, the tool was perceived as well aligned with users' daily research needs, offering useful features, quick access to the corpus, and support for consultation and comparison. String-based search was particularly efficient and fast.

2.3.2 Features Requiring Improvement

- **Similarity Score Information:** Users wanted more detailed information on how the Similarity Score and match figures (e.g., 10/17) are calculated. They suggested adding hover popups or tooltips for clarification.
- **Rating Feature:** Not considered useful. Users did not understand its purpose, comparing it to social media interactions (thumbs up/down). They felt only evaluations by accredited experts would be relevant and that differing academic perspectives present a challenge. The system should be revised to ensure that it does not trivialize philological analysis.
- **Search Icon (Magnifying Glass):** Not immediately understood. The prototype lacked tooltips, making the function hard to interpret. Contextual tooltips were suggested.
- **Source Feature Icon:** Unclear. Users did not understand the reference. They suggested specifying edition details when multiple versions are available.
- **Result Comparison Limit:** Users wanted to compare up to 5 or 6 results at once (currently limited to 3), without needing to start a new search in another tab.
- **Node Representation:** This feature could be misleading in some contexts, as node graphs are typically used in philology to illustrate structured or genealogical relationships between texts and/or manuscripts.
- **Comparison Criteria Display:** Users were confused by the presence of unselected criteria and mistakenly thought they could modify them, although these were preset by previous search settings.
- **Note Management Clarity:** Some users raised questions about the privacy or sharing of notes, expressing interest in managing their visibility.
- **Variant Graph Limitations:** The variant graph becomes difficult to read when dealing with fuzzy matches, many variants, or long texts. Users suggested improving the visual hierarchy,

adding indentation for apparatus, enabling collapsing of apparatus to reduce clutter, and ensuring line breaks align with the main critical edition.

- **Column View Match Visualization:** Users requested better highlighting of matching words, preferably in bold, and a clearer display of context in both the text and the apparatus.
- **Heat Map Readability:** Not intuitive. Users struggled to understand interaction logic and did not always recognize blue squares as indicators of occurrences. They requested greater interactivity, clearer indicators, and clickable elements to access texts or citations directly.
- **Saved Flows Management (Cloud):** Users expected a personal cloud-like space for saved flows, with options to make content public or private.
- **Ambiguous Apparatus Information:** The meaning of the number indicating apparatus, variant readings, lines, or occurrences was unclear. Some users preferred unaggregated or chronologically ordered results.
- **Line Graph Readability:** Lack of axis labels made interpretation difficult.
- **Historical Reliability of Map Localization:** The feature was considered unreliable for ancient texts. Geographical data may be inaccurate, particularly for itinerant authors or uncertain locations, which limits the map's usefulness for rigorous historical analysis.
- **Grammatical Analysis in the Dictionary:** Users requested this feature as a complement, especially for ancient languages like Greek.
- **Export Icon and Format Issues:** The export icon was ambiguous (resembled a download icon), and formats like CSV or JSON were unfamiliar. Users suggested removing unfamiliar formats and allowing export of selected parts via checkboxes.
- **Contextual Corpus Exploration Preferences:** Some users preferred starting with a keyword or text input followed by filtered results, instead of browsing.
- **Phrase Search Startup:** Not all users understood how to start a phrase search. Some expected copy/paste functionality, and others noted low visibility of relevant icons.
- **Aesthetic Aspects (Design):** Some users found the design functional but visually outdated.
- **Bilingual Author Handling:** For bilingual texts (e.g., Ancient Greek/Latin), users requested more nuanced navigation and language division logic.

2.3.3 General Evaluation

2.3.3.1 Navigation Experience

Intuitive and operationally aligned navigation experience:

- The browsing experience is perceived as intuitive and accessible: users navigate the tool easily without needing instructions. The interface is functional: clarity in organization is appreciated.
- The tool is generally perceived as well aligned with users' daily work needs: it offers useful functionalities, immediate access to the corpus, and support for consultation and comparison. With these specifics:

- for users not working directly on the texts, the tool’s utility is more occasional and related to specific research tasks.
- for those conducting in-depth philological research, the tool is an excellent starting point but does not replace interpretative and critical work, especially in cases of ambiguous or similar citations.

Aspects to pay attention to:

- Graphics. Some users report that the graphics, while functional, seem a bit “dated”.
- Management of bilingual authors. In the presence of bilingual texts (e.g. Ancient Greek/Latin), some users highlight the need for a more careful logic in navigation and language division.

2.3.3.2 Features

Positive and appreciated aspects:

- The interface is user-friendly and easily navigable.
- The ability to use one tool to work in multiple languages is appreciated.
- The functionalities are consistent with users’ operations: specifically, string search is particularly effective and generally fast and automated.
- The ability to view the context of a specific verse or source is appreciated.

Aspects to implement or clarify:

- Improve the intuitiveness of the icons (e.g. magnifying glass) and, more generally, simplify access points to the search. Provide informative hover texts or tooltips at key points in the workflow (e.g., the use of bold).
- Review the system to prevent automatic mechanisms or uncontrolled feedback from trivializing philological analysis, which could inadvertently attribute authority to unqualified evaluations and diminish the scientific value of textual comparisons.
- Allow users greater control over their content and workflows within the tool, including the option to make them public or keep them private.

2.4 Conclusions on the Prototype Test Results

The qualitative test confirmed that the *uBIQUity* prototype provides a solid foundation and already incorporates many well-designed and appreciated features. Users highlighted the intuitive interface, the clarity of the landing page, and the ease of navigation as key strengths, noting that the platform allows them to access *corpora*, perform searches, and compare texts with minimal effort. The language selection (Arabic, Ancient Greek, Latin) was perceived as immediate and effective, and

both direct text input and corpus browsing were considered intuitive and well aligned with users' research workflows.

Particularly appreciated features included: the match result visualization, whose structure and clarity allowed users to easily interpret correspondences between passages; the annotation and note-taking system, which was understood and valued for its integration with external tools such as Zotero; and the comparison and visualization tools — notably the node visualization, column view and variant graph — which effectively supported both close and distant reading approaches. The “Save Flow” function and the possibility of revisiting saved searches were also well received, as was the dictionary, highly valued for providing direct lexical insights. In general, users perceived the platform as consistent with their daily research needs, appreciating the possibility to conduct multilingual work and to visualize intertextual relationships in flexible, data-driven ways.

However, several areas for improvement were identified. Users requested greater clarity in icon design (e.g., magnifying glass, source icon) and clearer explanations of similarity scores and match metrics through tooltips or hover texts. The “Rating” system was considered unnecessary and potentially misleading, as it risks trivializing scholarly evaluation. Enhancements were also suggested for result comparison capacity (allowing more items to be compared simultaneously), for the readability and interactivity of the heat map and line graph, and for variant graph visualization, especially in the case of long or complex texts. Some participants indicated that the graphical layout, though functional, appeared visually outdated, and that a more refined approach is needed for the navigation of bilingual authors (e.g., Ancient Greek/Latin).

A recurring theme across interviews was the need for greater user control over personal content and workflows, including the ability to manage privacy and sharing settings for notes and saved workflows. Users expressed interest in a “cloud-like” environment where they could store, organize, and selectively share their work.

In conclusion, the test showed that *uBIQUity* is already perceived as an intuitive, efficient, and conceptually strong tool, well suited to the needs of scholars working in intertextual and philological research. Its combination of traditional methodologies and AI-supported functionalities was seen as particularly promising. Addressing the identified issues—especially those related to icon intuitiveness, visualization refinement, and user control—will be essential to consolidate the platform's usability and to ensure its full potential as a digital infrastructure for intertextual analysis in the humanities.

3. Training Material

Training on uBIQUity: The Legacy of Sacred Texts. Exploring Intertextuality Between the Ancient and Digital Worlds.

3.1 Short Description of the Course

This course begins by offering an overview of the reception and reuse of the sacred texts of Christianity and Islam within Christian literature composed in Greek and Latin—from the Patristic age to the late Byzantine period—and in classical Arabic Qur’ānic commentaries (*tafāsīr*) from the rise of Islam to the 15th century. Intertextual references, whether conscious or unconscious, embedded in ancient and medieval commentaries function as invisible “places of memory,” making the sacred texts “ubiquitous.” From this starting point, the course provides participants with a structured training path that integrates three complementary dimensions:

- **Theoretical foundations**, through the presentation of the *corpora* in Ancient Greek, Latin, and Arabic (Modules 1.1–1.2). These modules introduce the textual plurality of biblical traditions, the Qur’ān and its commentaries, and the role of the Prophet’s *Sunnah*, thereby situating intertextual phenomena within their historical, cultural, and exegetical contexts.
- **Methodological perspectives**, focused on the definition and classification of intertextuality (Modules 2.1–2.2). Here participants will explore how intertextual relationships are identified, described, and annotated in both biblical-patristic and Islamic traditions. This section also covers a guide for the creation of structured datasets, metadata, and filters (Module 3), which provide the conceptual framework for systematic analysis.
- **Digital practices**, developed through a sequence of hands-on modules (Modules 4–6). These include a step-by-step introduction to the functioning of the *uBIQUity* retrieval system, different search strategies (language-agnostic, language-aware, semantic), and the integration of results into meaningful analyses (Module 4). Module 5 offers a tutorial of the main functionalities of the *uBIQUity* tool, showing step by step—also through images—how to carry out intertextual research within the software. Finally, participants will engage with visualization systems for close and distant reading, node-based knowledge sharing, and note management (Module 6), which allow them to interpret, annotate, and disseminate their findings.

The course thus combines traditional philological methods with digital tools and AI-driven techniques, guiding users—students, doctoral candidates, researchers, and beyond—in exploring intertextuality in ancient texts through an interdisciplinary perspective.

Training materials for *uBIQUity*, covering all its aspects (theoretical, methodological, practical, and digital), will be delivered through multiple formats and activities. These will include lectures (in person or online) aimed at students, PhD fellows, and other researchers, as well as dissemination initiatives for non-specialist audiences through third mission activities. Hands-on workshops using the *uBIQUity* tool will also be organized by the WP8 team. Supporting resources will include slides, PDF documents, lecture recordings (audio and video), academic papers and selected studies. These interactive components will be available on the ITSERR platform (*Hortus*). As previously stated in the “Document Overview” (see above), this deliverable provides only the written and synthetic versions of the lessons.

3.2 Learning Outcomes

By the end of the course, participants will be able to:

1. Critically analyze biblical texts, recognizing and assessing their textual and exegetical plurality;
2. Distinguish between the Qur’ān and the Sayings of the Prophet (*ahādīth*), and critically analyze their role in Islamic exegetical traditions;
3. Identify and investigate the reuse of the sacred texts of Christianity and Islam in their respective ancient and medieval commentaries;
4. Acquire the theoretical foundations of intertextuality and apply them to ancient and medieval texts in different languages;
5. Use the *uBIQUity* tool to detect, analyze, and visualize intertextual relationships;
6. Create, document, and save complex research paths within the *uBIQUity* platform;
7. Apply both close reading and distant reading methods to specific *corpora*, integrating traditional philological approaches with digital analysis.

3.3 Target Audience

The course is designed for students, PhD fellows, researchers, professors, and educators in the humanities, especially those working in philology, history, religious studies, historical linguistics, exegesis, theology, Islamic studies, and digital humanities. It is suitable both for those interested in deepening traditional methodologies and for those wishing to acquire skills in using digital tools for the comparative analysis of texts.

3.4 Course Outline

The course is structured into modules that follow a progressive path, moving from the introduction of the *corpora* and their contexts to methodological perspectives, and finally to digital practices and hands-on tutorials.

Module 1.1: The Textual and Exegetical Plurality of Biblical Texts: Ancient Versions in Greek and Latin

Module 1.2: Islamic Scriptures: The Qur'ān, Its Commentaries, and the Prophet's *Sunnah*

Module 2.1: Biblical-Patristic Intertextuality. How to Classify and Annotate Intertextual Relationships

Module 2.2: Qur'ānic Commentaries (*Tafsīr*): Sources and Intertextuality

Module 3: Creating Structured Datasets: Data, Metadata, and Filters

Module 4: Inside *uBIQUity*: Understanding Information Retrieval to Identify Intertextual References

Module 4.1: Module Overview

Module 4.2: Information Retrieval

Module 4.3: Retrieval Strategies and the Hybrid Approach

Module 4.4: Language-Agnostic Search Strategies

Module 4.5: Language-Aware Search Strategies

Module 4.6: Semantic Search and Vector Embedding

Module 4.7: Putting It All Together

Module 4.8: Measuring the Performance of a Retrieval System

Module 4.9: Making Sense of the Data

Module 5: Comparative and Semantic Digital Analysis. Introduction to the Use of the *uBIQUity* Tool Developed by the Research Group. Case Studies: Greek, Latin, and Arabic

Module 6: Visualization Systems: Close Reading and Distant Reading; A Node-based UI to Build and Share Knowledge.

3.5 Modules (from 1 to 6)

Module 1.1 – The Textual and Exegetical Plurality of Biblical Texts: Ancient Versions in Greek and Latin

Learning Objectives

- Understand the plurality of Biblical texts in the ancient world and its reasons/origins
- Explore the compositional traits of a Biblical text
- Glimpse into the translation techniques of Biblical texts in Greek and Latin
- Learn about textual transmission
- Get to know the ancient versions of the Bible in Greek and Latin within their contexts

Introduction

This module explores the origin and diffusion of Biblical texts in antiquity and aims at highlighting the plurality of their forms. The module delves into an exploration of the main processes that made a Biblical text plural in antiquity, *i.e.* composition, translation, exegesis, and transmission, through the example of the book of Genesis.

Lesson Content

What is the Bible?

The word “Bible” comes from the Greek *biblia*, meaning “books”; the current name of the Scriptures that are considered sacred by different communities of believers around the globe is thus the antonomasia of a book. Yet the Bible was not born as a book; it is rather the result of a long historical and compositional process of different texts that were read, performed, and worshipped in Jewish communities in the Holy Land and the diaspora. The plural form of its name is thus apt to describe its nature of a book containing many books. This designation is already present in the Bible itself (cf. Daniel 9:2; 1 Maccabees 12:9; Romans 1:2 etc.).

If you open more than one modern edition of the Bible, you will surely notice differences in the order and number of books that are considered canonical by different communities: this is due to the historical processes of canonization, which led to a plurality of Bibles in the contemporary world. This kind of plurality is intrinsic to the Biblical texts and to their transmission and reception. Moreover, one does not have to imagine a single version of every book contained in the Bible; already in antiquity we can find traces of different stages of composition, as well as different versions. This is why there is no such thing as “the Bible” in antiquity, and the same applies for the contemporary world, in which different communities still have different versions of the Bible that they consider canonical and thus sacred. In this module, we will focus on the most prominent processes that led to this plurality, by taking the book of Genesis as an example. As one of the foundational biblical narratives, some form of this book is common to all versions of the Bible, making it ideal for your didactic purposes. As one can easily imagine, the narratives of Genesis have always been read and

commented upon by a huge number of ancient writers, both in Jewish and Christian environments, which makes the book interesting as long as the transmission processes go.

What processes could lead to textual plurality?

Let us now explore some processes that characterize the evolution of Scriptures into the plural corpus that we now know of. These processes are valid keys to explore the evolution of the Bible, intended as a collection of books. We will thus explore each process through the example of one book, the first of the collection in all its forms, the book of Genesis. The first process is **composition**. The redaction of the book took place in what can be inferred as a long time. Sometimes the processes behind the composition of a book are difficult to grasp and interpret, but they are made visible by some macrocharacteristics of the text, as for example repetitions, which are quite common in Biblical texts. In the case of Genesis, there are two accounts of the creation of humankind, in chapters 1 and 2. If we compare the two texts, it appears clear that they probably depend on different traditions of the same myth, since in Gen 1:26 the human being is created simultaneously in two genders, whereas in chapter 2 the creation myth only regards a male human being (2:7), who is later accompanied by a “helper” who can be his equal, the woman.

Genesis 1:26	Genesis 2:7; 18; 21-23
<p>Then God said, «Let us make man in our image, after our likeness. And let them have dominion over the fish of the sea and over the birds of the heavens and over the livestock and over all the earth and over every creeping thing that creeps on the earth». So God created man in his own image, in the image of God he created him; male and female he created them. (Transl. English Standard Version)</p>	<p>Then the Lord formed the man of dust from the ground and breathed into his nostrils the breath of life, and the man became a living creature. [...] Then the Lord God said, «it is not good that the man should be alone; I will make him a helper fit for him». [...] So the Lord caused a deep sleep to fall upon the man, and while he slept took one of his ribs and closed up its place with flesh. And the rib that the Lord God had taken from the man he made into a woman and brought her to the man. Then the man said, «This at last is bone of my bones and flesh of my flesh; she shall be called Woman, because she was taken out of Man» (Transl. English Standard Version)</p>

The two accounts can be felt as contradictory, yet they represent a normal situation in Biblical texts, which have been composed and assembled over long periods of time and through different pathways.

The so-called «Septuagint» is the first known Biblical translation; it was initiated during the Hellenistic era, in Alexandria, by the Jewish communities of the diaspora. In secondary literature, the term «Septuagint» can indicate the translation of the Torah/Pentateuch made by Jewish scholars at the Ptolemaic court during the 3rd cent. BCE, according to the story told in the *Letter of Aristeas*. It can also refer to the broader corpus of texts translated from Hebrew by Jews of the Hellenistic era or, even more broadly, designate the corpus of what was to become the Greek Bible in Christian environments, which includes a series of texts written directly in Greek. Modern editions of the Septuagint consider this last, enlarged sense of the word, which corresponds to the Christian idea of a Bible's First (or Old) Testament and includes 53 books.

The text of the translation from the Hellenistic era was revised already in antiquity to make it more literal as compared to the Hebrew text of the time. Fragments of those revisions, mostly coming from the I-II cent. C.E. are still available in the manuscript tradition. The three most relevant revisions are due to Aquila, Symmachus, and Theodotian. The remnants of their work are listed in a special apparatus in the latest edition of the Septuagint, edited by the German Academy of the Sciences in Göttingen. A page of the printed edition of Genesis, edited by John William Wevers in 1974, shows the edited text above and the second apparatus, containing, among others, the versions of Aquila, Symmachus, and Theodotian, at the bottom of the page.

An example of a variation found in a different translation can be found already on the first verse of Genesis, at the beginning of the Bible (quite literally). Genesis 1:1 in the Septuagint version starts with the words *ἐν ἀρχῇ*, «at the beginning». Aquila, author of a Jewish revision of the text from the 2nd cent. C.E., has a different translation, indicated in Wevers' edition with the siglum *α'*, followed by the variant *ἐν κεφαλαίῳ*, which has the same meaning but reminds more to the idea of a «head», as the Hebrew *b^erešit* of the Masoretic Text does. Both versions are legitimate and were known in antiquity to readers of Greek. The idea of a single translation in any ancient language is thus misleading and arguments on the evolution of Scriptures should not be based on such terms, since the evidence clearly points to the existence of multiple translations in any given language.

Coming to the Latin language, in the late 4th cent. C.E., **Jerome** produced a Latin translation of the Hebrew Bible and the Greek Second (or New) Testament that was to become extremely influential in the history of the Church. This version is normally referred to as *Vulgate*, although this term seems to have become a standard denomination for this version only after the council of Trent; before, the term was used by Jerome himself and his contemporaries to indicate the already existing versions of the Christian Bible in Latin. Those versions are known today as *Veteres Latinae*, «ancient Latin versions», and have survived only in fragmentary form. A modern edition of all the available textual material regarding ancient Latin translations of the Bible is being prepared by a group of scholars based at the Vetus Latina Institute in Beuron. Variations among these versions are common. For example, in Gen 1:2, Jerome translates the Hebrew *bohu* (Greek ἀκατασκεύαστος) as *vacua* (line H, siglum for Hieronymus). There were however other possible variant readings, translations that circulated and were considered legitimate renderings of the text, such as *incomposita*, *informis*, *rudis*,

and *incompta*. Different translations may have given readers different images of the primordial earth with no ordered form, which may have triggered different ideas and exegeses.

When dealing with the history of interpretation and exegesis, it is crucial to be acquainted with as many textual witnesses as possible, to glimpse at the variety and richness of Scripture that was probably available to ancient readers. It is important to be aware of this plurality, to avoid anachronistic ideas of the sacred texts.

What Happens in Textual Transmission?

Another layer of the history of Scriptures that caused textual plurality is **transmission** (or **tradition**), which is the history of how the Bible was copied through the centuries and spread all over the ancient worlds. In this centuries long process, linguistic variation is extremely common. It is impossible that the copying process produced no mistakes and/or intentional variation. In fact, the opposite is true. To quote only one simple example, the first verse of Genesis that we have seen above presents variant reading that derive from the textual tradition. This kind of variant readings is presented in the first apparatus, the area in the middle of the page in the printed edition. In this example, the verb that describes the creative action of God in the beginning is rendered in the Septuagint as **ἐποίησεν**, “he made”. Some manuscripts, however, show different possibilities, by using synonyms such as **ἔπλασεν**, “he modeled”, or **ἔκτισεν**, “he founded”. Each version is legitimate and must be chronologically and geographically assessed in order to find out its impact and reception. Biblical texts have been copied constantly and in different formats from antiquity to the advent of printed versions. This process led to the existence of **variant readings**, which go from simple scribal mistakes to more complicated attempts at exegesis and/or revision. Variant readings are gathered in the *apparatus criticus* of modern critical editions and enable the reader to go back the long line of tradition and get to know the text at its different historical stages of transmission. This textual material is extremely rich and meaningful to the study of the history of the Bible and should be made available in digital environments as well as in printed editions.

Greek and Latin Versions Still Available

The versions still available in printed editions today are indicated in the following two tables.

GREEK	LATIN
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Septuaginta (LXX) --- Critical editions: 1. R LXX = A. Rahlfs, R. Hanhart (eds), <i>Septuaginta: Id est Vetus Testamentum graece iuxta LXX interpretes. Editio altera</i>, Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2006 (A. Rahlfs, 1 ed. 1935). 2. G LXX = R. Hanhart, J.W. Wevers, J. Ziegler <i>et al.</i> (eds), <i>Septuaginta: Vetus Testamentum Graecum auctoritate Academiae Scientiarum Gottingensis editum</i>, Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1931. • Hexapla (H) --- Critical editions: 1. F H = F. Field (ed.), <i>Origenis Hexaplorum quae supersunt; sive, Veterum Interpretum Graecorum in totum Vetus Testamentum fragmenta</i>, 2 vols., Hildesheim: Olms, 1964 (re-print; Oxford, 1 ed. 1875) --- 2. [For a new critical edition of the extant Hexaplaric fragments, cf. http://hexapla.org/] • Novum Testamentum (NT) --- Critical edition: 1. NA NT = Eb. Nestle, Er. Nestle, B. Aland, K. Aland <i>et al.</i> (eds), <i>Novum Testamentum graece</i>, Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 28 ed. 2012 (E. Nestle, 1 ed. 1898). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vulgata (VULG) --- Critical edition: 1. W VULG = R. Weber, R. Gryson (eds), <i>Biblia Sacra iuxta Vulgatam Versionem</i>, Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 5 ed. 2007 (R. Weber, 1 ed. 1969). • Veteres Latinae (VL) --- Critical editions: 1. B VL = <i>Vetus Latina: Die Reste der altlateinischen Bibel nach Petrus Sabatier neu gesammelt und herausgegeben von der Erzabtei Beuron</i>, Freiburg i.B.: Herder, 1949-. Critical edition (27 vols. in total) not yet complete. 2. S VL = P. Sabatier (ed.), <i>Bibliorum Sacrorum latinae versiones antiquae seu Vetus Italica</i>, 3 vols., Reims: Reginaldus Florentain, 1743-1749.

The processes described in this lesson must be considered interwoven and mutually influential, producing variant readings of different nature. The distinction between the different processes mentioned above is not always evident and every variant reading that we encounter in the tradition can derive from any of them. The job of the Biblical scholar is to assess the different phenomena and place them in the flow of time, with philological and historical rigour. The complexity of the tradition requires a solid methodology and highly specific tools to make analysis possible. The *uBIQUity* tool tries to answer the call for a digital environment in which the available textual material is gathered and made visible to students, scholars, and communities, constituting yet another *tessera* in the mosaic of the endless reception history of Biblical texts.

Further Reading

- E. Bons, E. Prinzivalli, F. Vinel (eds.), *La pluralité des sens de la Bible. Lire les Écritures à l'époque des fondamentalismes*, Strasbourg: Presses Universitaires de Strasbourg, 2017.
- N. Fernández Marcos, *The Septuagint in Context. Introduction to the Greek Version of the Bible*, Leiden, Boston and Köln: Brill, 2000 (transl. from Spanish by Wilfred G.E. Watson).
- H.A.G. Houghton, *The Oxford Handbook of the Latin Bible*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2023.
- H. Najman, *Scriptural Vitality. Rethinking Philology and Hermeneutics*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2025.
- T. Rajak, *Translation and Survival. The Greek Bible of the Ancient Jewish Diaspora*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.
- M. Rösel, *Übersetzung als Vollendung der Auslegung*, Beihefte Zur Zeitschrift für die alttestamentliche Wissenschaft, Berlin: De Gruyter, 1994.

- K. Schmid, J. Schröter, *The Making of the Bible. From the First Fragments to Sacred Scripture*, Cambridge MA and London: Harvard University Press, 2021.
- E. Tov, *Textual Criticism of the Hebrew Bible. Second Revised Edition*, Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2001.

Module 1.2 – Islamic Scriptures: The Qur’ān, Its Commentaries, and the Prophet’s *Sunnah*

Learning Objectives

- Identify the structure, content, and religious significance of the Qur’ān in Islamic tradition
- Differentiate between the Qur’ān and the *Sunnah* as distinct yet complementary sources of authority
- Analyze the components of a *ḥadīth* and understand its role in transmitting the Prophet’s *Sunnah*
- Distinguish between *ḥadīth* collections and prophetic biographies (*sīrah*) in terms of form and function
- Recognize the key features of Qur’ānic commentaries (*tafāsīr*) and their role in interpreting the sacred text

Introduction

This module explores the foundational sources of Islamic thought and practice: the Qur’ān, the *Sunnah* of the Prophet, and the genre of Qur’ānic exegesis known as *tafāsīr*. It examines what types of sources these are, their structure and main features, and how they continue to shape Islamic theology, law, and devotional life. Understanding these categories is essential for anyone studying the history of religions, Islamic tradition, or scriptural interpretation more broadly.

Target

Students interested in the history of religions, with a particular focus on Islamic studies and its scriptures. No prior knowledge of these subjects is required for this lesson.

Lesson Content

What Is the Qur’ān?

The Qur’ān is the sacred scripture of Islam, regarded by Muslims as the literal transcription of the word of God (*kalām Allāh*), revealed in Arabic to the Prophet Muḥammad over a period of approximately 23 years, beginning in 610 CE. The text is composed in a distinctive form of rhymed

prose known as *sağ'*, which contributes to its oral memorability and rhetorical power. It consists of 114 *suwar* (sing. *sūrah*, chapters) and over 6,200 *āyāt* (sing. *āyah*, verses), both of varying length and style. Scholars generally divide the Qur'ānic revelations into two main periods: Meccan verses, revealed before the Prophet's migration (*hiğrah*) to Medina, and Medinan verses, revealed afterward. The Qur'ān is not a chronological or systematic treatise but a long divine monologue that combines legal, theological, eschatological, and narrative content. It frequently references earlier scriptures, polemicizes with its interlocutors, and situates its message within a broader monotheistic framework. From a scholarly perspective, its compilation and redaction, the interplay between oral and written transmission, and its intertextual relationships with Late Antique religious literature remain central topics of inquiry. Moreover, the Qur'ān's role in shaping Islamic law, theology, and ritual practice—as well as its reception history through exegesis (*tafsīr*)—highlights its enduring interpretive complexity.

What Is the Sunnah of the Prophet Muḥammad?

The *Sunnah* of the Prophet Muḥammad refers to his normative example—his sayings, actions, tacit approvals, and personal traits—which Muslims regard as a key source of religious guidance, second only to the Qur'ān. In matters of jurisprudence, orthopraxy, and social conduct, the *Sunnah* provides concrete and detailed guidance that complements and clarifies when the Qur'ān is concise or ambiguous. The *Sunnah* is primarily transmitted through individual reports known as *ḥadīth* (pl. *aḥādīth*), each typically consisting of two parts: the *isnād* (chain of transmitters) and the *matn* (textual content). A well-known example, transmitted in both al-Bukhārī and Muslim, states: «Actions are judged by intentions, and every person will have what they intended» a concise ethical maxim introduced by a rigorously authenticated chain of authorities. Originally passed down orally with meticulous memorization, *ḥadīth* transmission gradually transitioned into written form between the 2nd and 3rd centuries AH (8th–9th centuries CE), when scholars began compiling them into structured collections. Among these, six collections came to be recognized as canonical in *Sunnī* Islam (the *al-kutub al-sittah*), with *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī* and *Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim* holding the highest status due to their stringent criteria for assessing both the reliability of transmitters and the coherence of the content. While even these canonical works are not entirely free from reports later judged as weak, they remain central references in *Sunnī ḥadīth* scholarship. Beyond these core collections, many non-canonical or semi-canonical compilations also preserve weak or fabricated traditions, regional variants, and material excluded for reasons of authenticity or doctrinal concerns. To evaluate these reports, Muslim scholars developed sophisticated disciplines such as *ʿilm al-riğāl* and *ʿilm al-ḥadīth*, which analyze the credibility of transmitters, the plausibility of transmission chains, and the internal consistency of the reports themselves.

What Is the *Sīrah*?

Distinct from the *ḥadīth* literature is the *Sīrah al-Nabawīyyah* (or simply *Sīrah*), a biographical genre that narrates the life of the Prophet Muḥammad in a more continuous and narrative form. While the *Sīrah* (e.g., Ibn Ishāq’s *Sīrat Rasūl Allāh*, as transmitted by Ibn Hishām) includes episodes from the Prophet’s early life, prophetic mission, military campaigns, and social interactions, it lacks the formal *isnād* structure that characterizes the *ḥadīth*. As such, the *sīrah* is often considered less rigorous in terms of transmission standards, though it provides essential historical and contextual framing for many Qur’ānic verses and *ḥadīth* reports. In contrast, *ḥadīth* collections tend to be thematically organized (e.g., purification, prayer, commerce) and are primarily concerned with establishing legal and moral precedent through authenticated prophetic precedents. Together, *ḥadīth* and *sīrah* offer two complementary ways of transmitting the Prophet’s legacy and example, though from different literary and epistemological perspectives.

What Is the *Tafsīr*?

Tafsīr is the scholarly discipline of Qur’ānic exegesis, aimed at uncovering and articulating the meanings, implications, and contexts of the Qur’ānic text. Rooted in the Arabic verb *fassara* (“to explain” or “to interpret”), *tafsīr* encompasses a wide range of approaches, from grammatical and rhetorical analysis to theological, legal, and mystical interpretation. The development of *tafsīr* as a literary and scholarly genre began in the 2nd/8th century and reached a more systematic and expansive form in the 3rd/9th century with works like al-Ṭabarī’s *Ġāmi‘ al-bayān*. Over time, major exegetes such as al-Tha‘labī, al-Zamakhsharī, Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī, al-Qurṭubī, and Ibn Kathīr contributed to the formation of distinct exegetical traditions—rational (*‘aqlī*), transmitted (*naqlī*), legal (*fiqhī*), and esoteric (*bāṭinī*). While *tafsīr* was traditionally a written genre organized verse by verse, it also served broader hermeneutical functions: situating Qur’ānic verses within historical contexts (*asbāb al-nuzūl*), resolving apparent contradictions, and adapting the text’s guidance to evolving social, theological, and legal realities.

Further Reading

Reference Tools and Introductory Readings: *Qur’ān*

1. M.A. Amir Moezzi, *Le Coran silencieux et le Coran parlant : sources scripturaires de l’islam entre histoire et ferveur*, Paris: CNRS, 2011.
2. M.A. Amir Moezzi and G. Dye (eds.), *Le Coran des historiens*, Paris: Les Éditions du Cerf, 2019.
3. M. Campanini, *The Qur’an: Modern Muslim Interpretations*, trans. by C. Higgitt, London and New York: Routledge, 2011.

4. F. Déroche, *The One and the Many: The Early History of the Qur'an*, trans. by M.B. DeBevoise, Yale: Yale University Press, 2022.
5. N. Sinai, *The Qur'an: A Historical-Critical Introduction*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2017.
6. R. Tottoli, *The Qur'an: A Guidebook*, Berlin-Boston: De Gruyter, 2023.

Sunnah

1. J.A.C. Brown, *Hadith: Muhammad's Legacy in the Medieval and Modern World*, London: Oneworld, 2011.
2. J. Burton, *An Introduction to the Ḥadīth*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 1994.
3. W.A. Graham, *Divine Word and Prophetic Word in Early Islam: A Reconsideration of the Sources, with Special Reference to the Divine Saying or Ḥadīth Qudsī*. The Hague-Paris: Mouton, 1977.

Sites

1. <https://quran.com>
2. <https://sunnah.com>
3. <https://ahadith.co.uk>
4. <https://www.altafsir.com>
5. <https://shamela.ws>

2.1 – Biblical-Patristic Intertextuality. How to Classify and Annotate Intertextual Relationships

Learning Objectives

- Learn about the reuses of Biblical texts in patristic literature in Greek and Latin
- Discuss the spectrum of intertextual references (between quotation and allusion)
- Build an analysis of intertextual references based on semantics

Introduction

This module explores some strategies of textual reuse of the Bibles in Greek and Latin by ancient Christian authors in both languages. The nature of the intertextual relation created between the Biblical source text and the ancient author is analysed through a semantic classification that challenges the traditional distinction between literal quotation and free allusion and presents the textual reuse as a wide spectrum of possibilities. The semantic classification behind the conception of the *uBIQUity* tool is presented and discussed in this module.

Target

Students interested in the history of religions, particularly in Biblical studies, the transmission of its textual heritage, and the intertextual relationships among these texts.

Lesson Content

What Is Intertextuality?

Intertextuality is the relationship between two (or more) texts, describing how they relate one on the other and how the more ancient is re-used and re-signified in the more recent. Intertextuality has a clear chronological linear sense, yet the exploration of it can give us information on the more ancient text as well, especially regarding its transmission.

According to this perspective, no text appears out of nowhere or is totally original; on the contrary, every text can only be understood in relation to other texts, as well as to a shared code and contextual information. The processes that can be identified within intertextual relationships, with a special focus on the one between Biblical texts (in Greek and Latin) and ancient Christian authors (in the same languages), are the objects of this module.

The intertextual relations that are relevant to the study of Biblical texts are numerous. The most significant to our purposes and to the methodological framework of *uBIQUity* are as follows:

- A text of the Bible referring to another passage within the corpus and chronologically precedent; this kind of intertextuality is particularly meaningful, although not limited to, the study of the relations between the First (or Old) Testament and the Second (or New) Testament.
- A text of an ancient author who was a reader and interpreter of the Bible and uses its passages in his own work, explicitly quoting them or just alluding, rewriting, recreating them and/or their contents.
- A text of an ancient author who is citing another ancient author in reference to a Biblical passage, chapter, book, or episode. This kind of intertextuality highlights how intertextual relations are not necessarily limited to two actors but can involve more.

How Did Ancient Authors Use Biblical Texts?

Before delving into the strategies of Biblical reuse in patristic literature, let us give a concise definition of this field. Patristic literature refers to the work of the first Christian authors, among whom the so-called Church Fathers are included, who were active between the I and the V century C.E. These authors had a vast knowledge of Biblical literature, which they used not only in explicitly exegetical works such as commentaries, but also in other writings of literary, philosophical, and

apologetic nature. The reuses of Biblical texts within different works can differ widely and the study of intertextuality can tell us much about the diffusion of the source text (in our case, the Bible in its different versions), the mental library of those authors, their patterns of quotation, the common knowledge they assumed to be shared with their public, and much more. The research questions raised by the study of intertextuality in this wide corpus are potentially infinite and this course is meant to open the way to your own adventures with the *uBIQUity* tool, to find your own research questions and interests.

There are multiple ways of classifying intertextual references and making sense of their meaning. In traditional sources and editions of patristic literature, the go-to distinction is between voluntary and involuntary reference; this polar opposition has however several critical weaknesses, since it does not account for the full variety of intertextual references and is based on the evaluation of the intention of the author, which, by nature, is not easy to grasp critically. At the same time, the editions base the distinction between voluntary (and thus more literal) and involuntary (freer) on the presupposition that the text of the Bible is fixed and corresponds to the most updated edition available. This creates a methodological gap between editions, as well as giving the reader the illusion of the fixity of the Scriptural canon.

In the methodological approach of the *uBIQUity* platform, intertextual references are treated in a spectrum. The tool does not respond to the question of whether a certain passage is a voluntary quotation or an indirect allusion; what it does is it proposes connections between texts based on their semantic similarity (more on this later) and thus challenges any strict polarity that has traditionally been considered in the study of intertextuality. At the same time, the plurality of the Biblical textual material is considered in the analysis, thanks to the work on the variant reading present in the apparatus of critical editions. This approach permits more fluidity and a deeper understanding of how a mental library could work in the mind of an ancient Christian author dealing with Scriptures: he was trained in them, raised questions and proposed exegeses based on them, his whole thinking was deeply influenced by them; in this situation a fluid approach based on semantic similarity may open new avenues of research.

What is semantic similarity? In our framework, we consider semantic similarity in terms of the number of words that are similar between two texts. This similarity is not only calculated at the level of identical words (or tokens, every single specific instance of a word in a specific text), but also on other levels. Those proceed in concentric circles, between the narrowest, the Token, which activates if a word in text 1 is identical to a word in text 2, to include shared Lemmas, Roots, and Synonyms. Tools for the semantic analysis of Greek and Latin texts are included in the tool to reach this scope. The latest and largest circle, called Structure, refers to more difficult similarities, that pertain to the metaphorical or symbolic level and that may or may not be felt as similar or pertinent by different scholars.

In preparation for the tool, the team has identified and classified a group of intertextual references between Biblical texts and a selection of patristic works. After selecting the texts, the team tagged the references on the INCEpTION platform, dedicated to semantic annotation. The tagging is based on a complex tagset that signals the position of the reference within the corpus and its similarity measure.

How Are Intertextual References Classified?

The tagging of Latin references has been performed on Augustine's commentary on the book of Genesis known as *De Genesi ad litteram*. All references have been confronted with different texts of Genesis in Latin, available in modern editions.

The annotation process has allowed the team to highlight phenomena that would be impossible to detect using traditional digital tools to perform textual queries. The first advancement is the possibility to compare Augustine's text with different versions of the Bible, thus giving full light to the plurality that was intrinsic to Biblical texts in ancient times. When we detect differences between Augustine's text and the Biblical text, it may be a result of Augustine reading a different version of it than we do or suppose. The richness of Biblical textual material is normally not accessible to the digital user, who must go back to printed editions (if not to manuscripts) to fully visualize it. In this sense, the role of apparatus variants is invaluable; they may help reconstruct the circulation of different versions, as well as shed light on how ancient readers were engaging with the text of the Bible. A lot of information is contained in the apparatus, not only about the text per se, but also (and perhaps especially) about its early reception. Since we, as a generation of scholars, are called to perform a twist to the digital form of many textual traditions, processes as tagging give us the opportunity to engage in conversation about what needs to be preserved and how to do it best. In the case of the Bibles in Latin, a risk that needs to be addressed is the possibility of circularity of information about textual material. If a Biblical edition of the *Vetus Latina* (VL) is based on Augustine's texts, it is not an argument to say that Augustine was citing the VL version in his works: awareness of the sources helps both scholars and students avoid this risk and understand the possible dynamics among ancient texts, with a sound historical-critical method.

Similar principles work for the semantic annotation of Greek texts. The length of the string of numbers that appear in each tag, longer than the one used for Latin, expresses all semantic levels included in the concentric circles map.

In the case of Greek, the expansion of the semantic classification has allowed the team to discuss similar issues but through a slightly different angle. The role of tradition has been considered, since the language of Clement of Alexandria and consequently his textual relation to the Bible is indebted to the Alexandrian tradition, represented by authors such as Philo. The expansion of the corpus to authors that differ greatly in many aspects (time, purpose, literary genre, public) has led to a more

general picture of different possibilities of textual reuse of the Bible, always keeping an eye on its plurality.

Further Reading

- S. Alkier, *Intertextuality or the Decentralization of Meaning*, in “Religions”, 16:104 (2025). Open access: <https://www.mdpi.com/2077-1444/16/2/104>
- D. Dainese and A. Mambelli, *Intertestualità tra Bibbie e antichi commentari cristiani: l'esempio di simul nel De Genesi ad litteram di Agostino*, in “Lexicon Philosophicum: International Journal for the History of Texts and Ideas”, 11 (2023–2024), pp. 39-65. Open access: <https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/article/view/872/726>
- A. Mambelli, «Verranno giorni...» nel Vangelo di Luca: *l'influenza di Geremia LXX sulle profezie di Gesù riguardanti la distruzione di Gerusalemme*, in A. Mambelli (ed.) “*And from the daughter of Zion all her beauty is departed*” (Lam 1:6). *Reactions, Responses, and Reflections on the Fall of Jerusalem from the 1st to the 4th Century CE*, monographic section of “Annali di Storia dell’Esegesi”, 41, 2 (2024), pp. 275-310. Open access: <https://www.rivisteweb.it/doi/10.69071/115880>
- M. Vinzent, L. Mellerin, H.A.G. Houghton (eds.), *Biblical Quotations in Patristic Texts*, “Studia Patristica LIV”, vol. 2 (Papers presented at the Sixteenth International Conference on Patristic Studies held in Oxford 2011), Leuven-Paris-Walpole, MA 2013: <https://hal.science/halshs-01543067>

Module 2.2 – Qur’ānic Commentaries (*Tafsīr*): Sources and Intertextuality

Learning Objectives

- To recognize the characteristics and goals of Qur’ānic exegesis (*tafsīr*)
- To understand the sources of *tafsīr* and their relationship with the prophetic tradition
- To differentiate between major exegetical approaches, such as *tafsīr bi-’l-ma’thūr* and *tafsīr bi-’l-ra’y*

Introduction

This module explores the foundational sources of Qur’ānic commentaries (*tafsīr*) and their complex intertextual relationship with the Qur’ān and the Prophet’s *Sunnah*. It builds on Module 1.2 by showing how the Qur’ān and in particular the *Sunnah* interact within the exegetical tradition. The module highlights how intertextuality operates between these sources—through literal or non literal quotation and reinterpretation—revealing the dynamic dialogue that shapes Islamic exegesis. It

briefly examines how these sources are used together to interpret the Qur'ān, and how their interplay reflects broader theological, legal, and literary concerns in Islamic thought.

Target

Students interested in the history of religions, with a particular focus on Islamic studies and its scriptures.

Lesson Content

The Qur'ānic Commentary (*tafsīr*)

Tafsīr is one of the most prestigious and expansive genres within the Islamic written tradition, considered the core discipline of Qur'ānic sciences. Classical *tafsīr* often span multiple volumes and are designed to explain the Qur'ān chapter by chapter, verse by verse, and sometimes even word by word. *Tafsīr* reflects a cumulative tradition: exegetical material derived from the Prophet, his Companions, the Successors, and later authoritative scholars was preserved, elaborated, reinterpreted, and at times even discarded. This dynamic process generated a rich intertextual corpus that both anchored and shaped the genre.

Sources of Tafsīr

Classical exegetes drew from four major sources:

1. The Qur'ān itself: verses are often explained in light of other, thematically related verses. This type of intertextuality is explicit and literal, and the Qur'ānic text is never confused with its explanation.
2. The *Sunnah* of the Prophet: including sayings, actions, and episodes drawn from the *Sīrah*, is used to clarify or expand the meaning of Qur'ānic verses.
3. The legacy of the Prophet's Companions and Successors: these early authorities provided contextual and interpretive insight into the revelation.
4. Earlier *tafsīr* works: exegetes frequently cited and responded to the interpretations of their predecessors.

Tafsīr bi-'l-ma'thūr and tafsīr bi-'l-ra'y

Two broad methodological approaches developed in the tradition:

- *Tafsīr bi-’l-ma’thūr* relies on transmitted reports, including *ḥadīth*, sayings of the Prophet’s Companions, early interpretive traditions, and the authority of previous exegetes. This method emphasizes continuity with the earliest generations of Muslims and seeks to ground interpretation in authoritative sources passed down through reliable chains of transmission.
- *Tafsīr bi-’l-ra’y* allows for independent reasoning in interpreting the Qur’ān, using tools from grammar, jurisprudence, and theology, as long as it does not conflict with accepted transmitted sources.

Intertextuality in *Tafsīr*

Tafsīr is a deeply intertextual genre. While Qur’ānic verses are cited literally and never confused with their explanation, the Prophet’s *Sunnah*—and other authoritative sources—is integrated more flexibly and in a variety of forms. The *Sunnah*, including *ḥadīth* reports and *Sīrah* (biographical narratives), serves not only to clarify ambiguous Qur’ānic passages but also to expand and enrich their legal, theological, and ethical implications across a range of domains.

Exegetes used a wide variety of sources:

- canonical collections of *ḥadīth* (e.g., al-Bukhārī, Muslim),
- non-canonical compilations,
- unreliable or weakly authenticated materials,
- other *tafsīr* texts.

A single *ḥadīth* might appear in several versions, adapted in structure, wording, or chain of transmission, and linked to different Qur’ānic verses than those found in standard *ḥadīth* collections.

Muḥaddithūn vs. mufassirūn

These variations reflect the differing priorities of *ḥadīth* collectors and Qur’ānic exegetes in how they cited and used *aḥādīth*. While *muḥaddithūn* (scholars of *ḥadīth*) focused on preserving only reports with reliable and complete chains of transmission, *mufassirūn* (exegetes) were more concerned with the interpretive usefulness of a report. As a result, they often included *aḥādīth* that were relevant to the meaning of a verse, even if this meant using material without full *isnāds* or canonical status. Thus, *tafsīr* functions not only as a commentary on the Qur’ān but also as a site of dynamic textual reuse, where earlier Islamic traditions are reinterpreted to serve evolving exegetical goals.

Further Reading

Reference Tools and Introductory Readings: Tafṣīr

1. H. Berg, *The Development of Exegesis in Early Islam: The Authenticity of Muslim Literature from the Formative Period*, Richmond: Curzon, 2000.
2. A. Görke and J. Pink (eds.), *Tafṣīr and Islamic Intellectual History: Exploring the Boundaries of a Genre*, New York: Oxford University Press in association with the Institute of Ismaili Studies, 2014.
3. G.R. Hawting and A.-K.A. Shareef (eds.), *Approaches to the Qur'ān*, London: Routledge, 1993.
4. A. Rippin, *Approaches to the History of the Interpretation of the Qur'ān*, Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1988.
5. M.A.A Shah and M.A. Abdel Haleem (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Qur'anic Studies*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2020.

Module 3 – Creating Structured Datasets: Data, Metadata, and Filters

Learning Objectives

- Get to know modern critical editions of Biblical and patristic texts in Greek and Latin
- Understand what it means to construct structured datasets from these editions
- Learn how metadata are defined, structured, and encoded
- Explore the structure and logic of the Greek, Latin and Arabic *uBIQUity* datasets
- Discover the types of filters and searches made possible by this encoding

Introduction

In this module, we explore the process of transforming data from critical editions of Biblical and patristic texts into structured datasets—that is, collections of textual information and metadata prepared for both human analysis and machine processing. We will focus on the key distinctions between data (the content itself) and metadata (information about the content: where it comes from, how it is used and how it connects to other texts). You will also learn how this material must be encoded using digital standards (such as XML-TEI, RDF-OWL, JSON-LD) to ensure searchability, interoperability and reproducibility.

The *uBIQUity* project currently includes multiple language-specific datasets—Greek, Latin, and Arabic—each built on different textual traditions, editorial choices and encoding strategies. These datasets enable advanced querying through a range of filters, including author (by name, period or geographical context), biblical book, textual version (e.g., Septuagint, *Vulgate*) and type of intertextual match—whether exact, inflectional, root-based, synonymic or inferred allusion.

Creating a dataset is not just about digitizing a text. It involves a series of deliberate choices:

- What do we encode?
- How do we encode it?
- Why do we choose a specific structure, format, or annotation model?

These decisions are never neutral. They shape the types of questions we can ask of the data and the kinds of insights we can gain in return. In the digital humanities, encoding is interpretation.

Target

Scholars and students in the humanities with little or no technical background who want to understand how religious texts (or textual data more generally) and their metadata can be modeled, structured, and analyzed in a digital environment.

Lesson Content

The Ancient Versions of the Bible Today

The Bible, in both Greek and Latin, has reached us through a complex and rich tradition of variant versions. The plurality of Biblical texts is not a modern accident: it is intrinsic to their history. Each ancient version—whether a Septuagint manuscript or a *Vetus Latina* codex—tells its own story. Modern editors must choose how to represent this richness. The result? Different editions, different purposes, different editorial philosophies.

As for the Greek Bible, the three main traditions represented by the Septuagint (LXX), the Hexapla (H), and the Second (or New) Testament (NT) are accessible in the critical editions listed below:

1. The *Göttingen Septuagint* (G_LXX: *Septuaginta: Vetus Testamentum Graecum auctoritate Academiae Scientiarum Gottingensis editum*) represents the most comprehensive critical edition of the Greek First (or Old) Testament. It includes two critical apparatus (the former for the textual evidence of the Greek text of the Septuagint, the latter for the tradition of Origen's *Hexapla*). However, this edition remains incomplete, with the following books still in progress: *Canticum*, *Iosue*, *Iudices*, *Maccabaeorum IV*, *Paralipomenon liber I*, *Prouerbia* and *Regnorum libri*. For these books, one can rely on the *editio altera* (R_LXX), a revision by Robert Hanhart of Alfred Rahlfs' 2006 (¹1935) *Handausgabe*, which is regarded by scholars as a “provisional” edition.
2. The ancient edition of the Greek Bible carried out by Origen of Alexandria and known as *Hexapla* (H) or “Sixfold” (insofar as it presented the Hebrew text of the First [or Old] Testament, the Hebrew text in Greek characters, and the Greek versions of Aquila, Symmachus, the Septuagint, and Theodotian in six parallel columns) is available in the edition

of F. Field (ed.), *Origenis Hexaplorum quae supersunt; sive, Veterum Interpretum Graecorum in totum Vetus Testamentum fragmenta*, 2 vols., Hildesheim: Olms, 1964 (re-print; Oxford, 1875) (= F_H). The information contained in Field's edition converges with the second apparatus of the Göttingen Septuagint editions.

3. A new critical edition of the extant Hexaplaric fragments has been started with the series "Origen's Hexapla: A Critical Edition of the Extant Fragments", but currently includes only J.D. Meade, *A Critical Edition of the Hexaplaric Fragments of Job 22-42*, Leuven: Peeters, 2020.
4. The Greek text of the Second (New) Testament (NT) has been edited by Eb. Nestle, Er. Nestle, B. Aland, K. Aland *et al.* (eds.), *Novum Testamentum graece*, Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012 (E. Nestle, 1898) (= NA_NT).

As for the Latin Bible, the text of Jerome's *Vulgate* (VULG)—which became the standard reference biblical text for the Latin West already in Late Antiquity—is available in the edition of:

1. R. Weber, R. Gryson (eds.), *Biblia Sacra iuxta Vulgatam Versionem*, Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2007 (R. Weber, 1969) (=W_VULG).

The other Latin versions of the First (or Old) and the Second (or New) Testaments, which circulated in the Christian world both before and after Jerome's *Vulgate*, are available in:

2. the eighteenth-century edition of the Benedictine monk P. Sabatier (ed.), *Bibliorum Sacrorum latinae versiones antiquae seu Vetus Italica*, 3 vols., Reims: Reginaldus Florentain, 1743-1751 (=S_VL). This edition includes both the First and the Second Testament, but, given the date and circumstances of its publication, cannot be considered a scientifically accurate critical edition
3. the modern critical editions in the series *Vetus Latina: Die Reste der altlateinischen Bibel nach Petrus Sabatier neu gesammelt und herausgegeben von der Erzabtei Beuron*, Freiburg i.B.: Herder, 1949- (=B_VL). This critical edition is not complete and currently features 27 vols.

What About Those Versions in the Digital Era?

Digitizing ancient texts is not a mechanical process. It requires both technical decisions (Which format? Which structure? Which tools?) and epistemological reflection (How do we represent textual uncertainty? Conflicting versions? Editorial interventions?). Moreover, to build a dataset from a critical edition, we must also answer a meta-question: *What exactly are we encoding—and why?*

The *uBIQUity* tool is not just a digital archive. It reflects a broader data-driven approach to the transmission and reception of the Bible in multiple languages and traditions.

Types of Digital Editions: A Necessary Distinction

Before reviewing the current status of the digitization of key editions, it is important to distinguish between different types of “digitization”:

Type of Resource	Description	Usability
Scanned PDF	Image-based, non-editable	Low (read-only, no data extraction)
E-book format	Digitally readable, sometimes searchable	Medium (closed formats, limited export)
Structured digital edition (born-digital)	Encoded in XML/TEI or in RDF, interoperable	High (machine-processable, FAIR)

Current State of Digital Availability

- The critical apparatus is included in a digital edition exclusively for the Göttingen Septuagint, where both the critical apparatus and the Hexaplaric apparatus are accessible and can be viewed separately from the edited text on the Logos (<https://www.logos.com/>) and *Accordance* (<https://www.accordancebible.com>) platforms. However, these are proprietary services that require significant costs for access.
- The digitized edition of Rahlfs-Hanhart, too, is accessible through Logos by paying a fee (<https://www.logos.com/product/7080/septuagint>).
- The two volumes of Field’s edition are available on Archive.org, but the PDFs that can be downloaded from Archive are not of good quality (<https://archive.org/details/origenishexaplor01origuoft/page/n5/mode/2up> + <https://archive.org/details/origenishexaplor02origuoft/page/n1/mode/2up>).
- The digitized edition of Nestle-Aland edition of the Greek Second (or New) Testament is also available through Logos upon payment of a fee (<https://www.logos.com/product/29980/nestle-aland-greek-new-testament-28th-edition-with-critical-apparatus>). The critical apparatus is also available there, although the variant readings are not linked to the text but available as a separate document.
- The digitized edition of the Weber-Gryson edition of Jerome’s *Vulgate* is available on the website of the Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft (<https://www.die-bibel.de/wissenschaftliche->

[ausgaben/vulgata](#)), but without the apparatus, which can be found in Logos (<https://www.logos.com/product/17846/biblia-sacra-vulgata-bsv-with-apparatus>).

- The three volumes of Sabatier’s edition are available on Archive.org, but the PDFs that can be downloaded from Archive are not of good quality (<https://archive.org/details/bibliorumsacroru01saba/page/n7/mode/2up> + <https://archive.org/details/bibliorumsacroru02saba/page/n7/mode/2up> + <https://archive.org/details/Sabatier3>). WP8 obtained for research purposes the first two digitized volumes of Sabatier’s edition through Accordance (for a fee: <https://www.accordancebible.com/product/vetus-latina-ot/>). These digitized documents were reviewed and cleaned of inaccuracies by the WP8 team. The third volume (containing the Second [or New] Testament in the *Vetus Latina*) was digitized by some WP8 team members with OCR (= Optical Character Recognition) via Transkribus (<https://www.transkribus.org/>) from the printed edition.
- The Beuron editions of the *Vetus Latina* Bible are not available in any digitized format. WP8 team has currently achieved with OCR technology the first digitized volume of Beuron’s edition (containing Genesis in the *Vetus Latina*) for research aims, with the assistance of TREVENTUS Mechatronics GmbH (<https://www.treventus.com/about/company>).

Most of these “digital editions” are not usable as *datasets*. To study the intertextual transmission of the Bible computationally, scholars must first create their own structured, annotated versions—because most editorial content remains locked behind images, proprietary formats, or incomplete metadata.

How to Build a Dataset

Now that we have seen what editions exist and how (in)accessible they are in digital formats, let’s shift perspective. How do we move from editions to *datasets*? What does it mean to turn these texts into a searchable research infrastructure?

What Is a Dataset?

A dataset is a structured collection of information designed to be searchable, analyzable and machine-readable. Unlike a simple text in digital format, a dataset includes both content and context—the metadata that tells you what something is, where it comes from and how it relates to other information. This structured approach powers everything from search engines to AI models, but in the humanities, it enables a new kind of scalable close and also distant reading, allowing scholars to move seamlessly between individual passages and large-scale patterns. In historical and philological research, this means that a dataset must capture not only what a text says, but also where it comes from, how it varies and how it connects to other texts, depending on the scholarly perspective from which the text is viewed.

This would often mean representing key features such as:

- content (the words themselves)
- context (author, date, place, variants, links)
- provenance (edition, manuscript, witness)

What we choose to encode—and how we structure it—depends on our research perspective. This interpretive dimension is clearly visualized in Sahle’s influential model of digital scholarly editing, where modeling sits at the center of the “digital edition wheel”. Here, modeling mediates between source material and output—shaping what kinds of questions can be asked of the data. That is why dataset construction is never neutral. We do not just digitize texts—we model them, based on scholarly questions and theoretical frameworks. Data modeling is interpretation and it requires domain expertise: only scholars who understand the textual tradition can create meaningful annotations and relationships.

The *uBIQ*uity Dataset: Architecture and Design Choices

Now that we’ve seen how dataset construction is shaped by research goals and interpretive modeling, let’s turn to a concrete example: the *uBIQ*uity dataset. *uBIQ*uity is not a monolithic corpus. It is a multi-source, multi-language, multi-layered ecosystem of datasets designed to support the detection, analysis and retrieval of biblical (and Islamic) intertextuality in Greek, Latin (and Arabic) texts. Its design choices—from corpus selection to metadata structure—reflect specific philological priorities, while enabling machine-readable and reproducible workflows. The Greek and Latin *corpora* cover two main textual domains:

- Scriptures: Greek and Latin biblical texts in their major scholarly editions and versions (G_LXX, R_LXX, NA_NT, W_VULG, B_VL, S_VL)

- Ancient Authors: Patristic and late antique authors in Greek and Latin from the first centuries CE onward

All *uBIQUity* texts are XML-encoded (TEI, OSIS, TEI-EpiDoc) and accompanied by contextual metadata, so that each intertextual match resulting from a search is enriched with information about:

- the source author and work
- the biblical version and (where available) critical apparatus variants
- the type of intertextual relationship (Token, Lemma, Root, Synonym, Structure)

This metadata architecture is what turns *uBIQUity* from a digital archive into a searchable, filterable and analyzable research dataset.

Encoding and Metadata: Giving Structure to *uBIQUity* Texts

When we say that all *uBIQUity* texts are XML-encoded and enriched with metadata, what does that mean? XML, or *Extensible Markup Language*, is a markup language—that is, a way of adding structured tags to a text so that computers can understand not only the words, but also their role and meaning. Instead of just storing plain characters, XML uses markup—labels that wrap around parts of the text to explain what they are. This process of turning plain data into structured, machine-readable data is called encoding. Encoding is what transforms a simple digital transcription into a resource that can be searched, filtered, and analyzed. With encoding, we don't just record what the text says—we model what the text is and how its elements function. For example, the tag `<author>Ambrose</author>` tells us this is not just a string of characters, but the name of an author. It's not just characters on a screen—it's a structured piece of information that can be linked, retrieved or compared across the dataset. But XML on its own would be useless if every project invented its own tags. That's why we rely on encoding schemas—sets of community-agreed rules that specify which tags to use and how to use them. These schemas guarantee consistency, interoperability and long-term usability.

In *uBIQUity*, three main standards are used:

- TEI (*Text Encoding Initiative*): the gold standard for encoding scholarly texts. In *uBIQUity*, TEI is applied in two domains:
 - Ancient Authors: TEI encodes both the Greek text itself (chapters, sections, paragraphs) and the author/work metadata (identifiers like TLG, VIAF, Wikidata; floruit; geographical context).
 - Scriptures' datasets: TEI is used for encoding apparatus strings and manuscripts, so that variant readings and witnesses can be linked back to the edited biblical text.

Example (author metadata in TEI):

```

<persName xml:lang="la">Clemens Romanus et Clementina Theol.</persName>
<idno type="TLG">TLG: 1271</idno>
<idno type="VIAF" corresp="https://viaf.org/en/viaf/46860095">46860095</idno>
<idno type="WIKIDATA"
corresp="https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q42887">Q42887</idno>
<birth notBefore="0050" notAfter="0199"> 1rst/2nd cent. CE (?) <settlement
type="city">unknown</settlement> <country key="">unknown</country> </birth>

<death notBefore="0050" notAfter="0199">1rst/2nd cent. CE (?) <settlement
type="city">unknown</settlement>
<country key="">unknown</country>
</death>
<floruit>
<date notBefore="0050" notAfter="0199"/>
<settlement type="city">Rome</settlement>
<country key="IT">Italy</country></floruit>
</person>

```

- OSIS (*Open Scripture Information Standard*), a schema specifically designed for biblical texts. In *uBIQUity*, OSIS structures the *Scriptures* domain (Greek and Latin Bibles), marking biblical passages by book, chapter, and verse in a standardized way.

```

<verse sID="rlxx_deuteronomy.7.1" osisID="rlxx_deuteronomy.7.1" />Ἐὰν δὲ
εἰσαγάγῃ σε κύριος ὁ θεός σου εἰς τὴν γῆν,[...]<verse eID="rlxx_deuteronomy.7.1"
/>

```

- TEI-EpiDoc: a specialization of TEI originally designed for inscriptions and fragmentary texts. In *uBIQUity*, TEI-EpiDoc is used for the Latin Ancient Authors corpus, because these texts are sourced from the Corpus Corporum repository, which distributes them in EpiDoc format.
 - The literary texts themselves (e.g. passages from Ambrose or Augustine) are therefore preserved in TEI-EpiDoc.
 - The author and work metadata, however, have been encoded separately in standard TEI. This includes identifiers (VIAF, Wikidata), biographical data, floruit, geographical provenance, and editorial references.

```

<div3 n="2" subtype="section"><head>§ 2</head>
<p>omne autem opus, quod sacris uoluminibus continetur, <lb n="10"/>
aduentum domini nostri Iesu Christi, quo missus a patre <lb/>
ex uirgine per spiritum homo natus est, et dictis nuntiat et <choice

```

```
n="0.69"><note n="326">factis</note><corr n="142">actis</corr></choice> <lb/>
  exemplis et confirmat exemplis.</p></div3>
```

Together, these schemas enable *uBIQUity* to represent very different kinds of information—biblical verses, patristic works and metadata, textual variants and manuscript witnesses—within a single, interoperable framework. The tags are not decorative: they provide context. They specify which edition a passage comes from, which biblical version is being cited, which manuscript supports a variant, and which ancient author is reusing it. In other words, encoding turns text into structured knowledge.

From XML to Linked Open Data

XML gives us a hierarchical structure for encoding texts, but it is limited when we want to connect data across different projects or disciplines. To achieve that, we move into the world of the Semantic Web. The Semantic Web is an extension of the current web where information is not only displayed for humans, but also structured so that machines can understand, combine, and reuse it. Its basic building block is RDF (*Resource Description Framework*). RDF expresses information as simple triples:

- subject – predicate – object

For example:

```
:Clemens_Alexandrinus a foaf:Person ;
rdfs:label "Clement of Alexandria"
owl:sameAs <http://viaf.org/viaf/46860095> .
```

Here we are saying:

- the subject is Clement of Alexandria
- he is a (a) Person
- his label is “Clement of Alexandria”
- he is the same as the VIAF authority record.

This is no longer just a string in one dataset: it becomes part of the global Linked Open Data (LOD) cloud, where scholars can connect and compare information across multiple resources (e.g. VIAF, Wikidata, other *corpora*).

Why Does This Matter for *uBIQUity*?

At the moment, our data are encoded in XML (TEI, OSIS, EpiDoc) and perfectly usable inside the project. But by progressively converting key parts of this data (authors, works, biblical variants, witnesses) into RDF, we could:

- make *uBIQUity* interoperable with other digital *corpora*,
- allow SPARQL queries like “*Find all authors in VIAF who cite Genesis 1:26 in Latin before 500 CE*”,
- and guarantee that our data follow the FAIR principles:
 - Findable (with stable identifiers like VIAF/Wikidata),
 - Accessible (in open formats, not locked in PDFs),
 - Interoperable (compatible with other ontologies and projects),
 - Reusable (ready to be cited, analyzed and re-purposed).

In other words: XML gives us structure; RDF gives us connections. The future step for *uBIQUity* is to move from isolated datasets to a networked, semantic ecosystem where our texts “talk” to other scholarly resources on the web.

Filters in Action

The *uBIQUity* tool allows you to filter:

- By language, corpus and/or author, period, region, textual tradition
- By semantic similarity level (Token, Lemma, Root, Synonym, Structure)
- By book, chapter, or even type of reuse

These filters are the digital equivalent of close reading—at scale.

The Arabic Dataset

The Arabic dataset within *uBIQUity* is an extensive and heterogeneous corpus for the study of intertextuality in Islamic literature. It brings together foundational genres of the Islamic textual tradition—Qur’ān, *ḥadīth*, *sīrah*, and *tafsīr*—each of which plays a distinctive role in shaping the transmission and interpretation of sacred knowledge.

The corpus includes, first and foremost, the Qur’ān, the central text of Islam and the cornerstone of the exegetical tradition. Secondly, the dataset encompasses the *ḥadīth* collections, which record the sayings and actions of the Prophet Muḥammad. The corpus is not limited to the six canonical Sunni collections (*kuṭub al-sittah*) but also incorporates: non-canonical collections; Shī‘ī collections; collections considered less reliable by later scholars, and collections compiled after the canonization

that took place in the 10th century. In total, approximately seventy *ḥadīth* collections have been integrated, offering a wide and balanced representation of the diversity of the Islamic transmission. The dataset further includes four *sīrah* works—biographies of the Prophet—that complement the *ḥadīth* corpus by preserving narrative and historiographical materials that often reappear in exegetical literature. Finally, the dataset is completed by nearly one hundred Qur’ānic commentaries (*tafsīr*), dating from the 8th to the 15th century. These monumental works, frequently extending across dozens of volumes, constitute an extraordinary repository of exegetical practices and interpretive strategies.

Sources and Preparation

The Arabic dataset builds upon the vast digital resources of the *Open Islamicate Texts Initiative* (OpenITI), a collaborative project founded in 2016 by Maxim Romanov, Sarah Bowen Savant, and Matt Miller. OpenITI aggregates texts from major online repositories (e.g. *al-Maktaba al-Shāmila*, *al-tafsir.com*, *sunnah.com*, and others), providing a unified corpus for computational research in Islamicate studies. These online libraries have digitized printed editions either through manual transcription or *Optical Character Recognition* (OCR), thus making a large portion of the classical Islamic heritage available in machine-readable form.

For WP8, the Arabic dataset was curated through the selection, verification, and harmonization of texts drawn from these sources. The OpenITI corpus provides texts in plain TXT format, often already containing basic internal metadata (for instance, chapter and verse numbers in Qur’ānic texts, or book, chapter, and entry numbers in *ḥadīth* collections).

Metadata Architecture

During the testing phase of the prototype tool, testers often found the metadata overwhelming, inconsistent, incomplete, unclear, or overly technical—a consequence of their provenance from the OpenITI corpus and other legacy data models. In response, significant efforts have been made to refine and standardize the metadata presentation: missing information has been added, the field order and nomenclature have been harmonized, and visual clutter reduced.

A defining feature of the current Arabic dataset is its rich and structured metadata layer, which ensures that every text is accompanied by standardized biographical and bibliographical information. This architecture enables contextualized searches and enhances data interoperability across the *uBIQUity* environment. Each record is described through a metadata block containing key identifiers and descriptive fields—including the author’s name, work title, modern edition, editor, and publisher (information provided both in Arabic and in transliteration), chronological data (both Hijrī and Gregorian dates), source collection, and original file path. These improvements are being progressively implemented to increase clarity, consistency, and usability.

An example of the metadata block placed at the top of each TXT file is shown below:

```
#####OpenITI#

#META# 000.SortField      :: NO ATA
#META# 001.BookTYPE      :::Hadīṭ
#META# 002.BookURI       :: #Shamela_0001727
#META# 010.AuthorAKA     :: Muslim b. al-Ḥajjāj Abū al-Ḥasan al-Qashīrī al-Nisābūrī
#META# 011.AuthorNAME    :: مسلم بن الحجاج أبو الحسن القشيري النيسابوري
#META# 012.AuthorBORN    :: 815/206
#META# 013.AuthorDIED    :: 875/261
#META# 014.AuthorBIRTHPLACE :::Nishapour
#META# 015.AuthorGEOBIRTHPLACE::: 36°12' N 58°48' E
#META# 016.AuthorDEATHPLACE :::Nasarabad
#META# 017.AuthorGEODEATHPLACE:::36° 1' 6" N, 58° 31' 27" E
#META# 018.AuthorWORKPLACE ::: Nishapour, Nasarabad
#META# 019.AuthorGEOWORKPLACES ::: 36°12' N 58°48' E, 36° 1' 6" N, 58° 31' 27" E
#META# 020.BookTITLE     :: صحیح مسلم
#META# 021.BookTITLEalt  :: Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim
#META# 022.BookVOLS      :: 5
#META# 030.LibURI        :: Shamela_0001727
#META# 031.LibREADONLINE ::: https://archive.org/details/26741
#META# 032.LibURL        :: https://archive.org/details/26741
#META# 040.EdALL         :: NO DATA
#META# 041.EdEDITOR      :: محمد فؤاد عبد الباقي
#META# 042.EdEDITORalt   :: Muḥammad Fū'ād 'Abd al-Bāqī
#META# 043.EdPUBLISHER   ::: دار احياء التراث العربي
#META# 044.EdPUBLISHERalt ::: Dār Iḥyā' al-Turāth al-'Arabī
#META# 045.EdPLACE       :: Beirut
#META# 046.EdYEAR        :: NO DATA
#META# 047.EdISBN        :: NO DATA
```

Therefore, these metadata fall into two main domains:

- Biographical metadata, detailing the author's name (in Arabic and transliteration), birth and death dates (Hijrī and Gregorian), and places of birth, death, and activity—each complemented by geographical coordinates that feed into *uBIQUity*'s interactive mapping system.
- Bibliographical metadata, documenting the title of the work (in Arabic and transliteration), the details of its modern digitized edition (editor, publisher, place and date of publication, number of volumes), and stable links to the online repositories hosting the text.

This dual structure ensures that each text is not merely a string of words but a fully contextualized scholarly object—anchored in time, space, and intellectual tradition. With this design, the Arabic dataset functions as far more than a textual archive: it is a research infrastructure enriched with historical, geographical, and bibliographical information, capable of supporting complex filters and intertextual queries across centuries of Islamic scholarship. It provides the necessary backbone for exploring how Qur'ānic and prophetic language was transmitted, reused, and reinterpreted within the vast exegetical heritage of the Islamicate world.

Further Reading

- R. Afferni, A. Borgna, M. Lana, P. Monella, and T. Tambassi, “...But What Should I Put in a Digital Apparatus?”. *A Not-so-obvious Choice. New Types of Digital Scholarly Editions*, in *Advances in Digital Scholarly Editing: Papers Presented at the DiXiT Conferences in The Hague, Cologne, and Antwerp*, Leiden: Sidestone, 2017, pp. 141-144.
- F. Ciotti F., *Digital Humanities. Metodi, strumenti, saperi*, Roma: Carocci, 2023.
- A. Ciula, Ø. Eide, C. Marras, P. Sahle, *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities. Thinking in Practice*, Cambridge: Open Book, 2023.
- D. Dainese and A. Mambelli, *Intertestualità tra Bibbie e antichi commentari cristiani: l’esempio di simul nel De Genesi ad litteram di Agostino*, in “Lexicon Philosophicum: International Journal for the History of Texts and Ideas”, 11 (2023–2024), pp. 39-65. Open access: <https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/article/view/872/726>
- C. Martignano, *A Conceptual Model to Encourage the Development and Reuse of Apps for Digital Editions*, in “Umanistica Digitale”, 5/10 (2021), pp. 71-88.
- G. Milanese, *Filologia, letteratura, computer. Idee e strumenti per l’informatica umanistica*, Milano: Vita e Pensiero, 2020.
- P. Sahle, *Digitale Editionsformen, Teil 3, Textbegriffe und Recodierung*, Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2013.

Module 4 – Inside *uBIQUity*: Understanding Information Retrieval to Identify Intertextual References

Module 4.1 – Module Overview

Learning Objectives

- Understand the scope and structure of Module 4 within the broader course
- Recognize the rationale for a technical module within a humanities-focused curriculum
- Know what to expect in terms of methods, terminology, and learning goals

Introduction

This lesson provides an overview of Module 4, which is dedicated to understanding how the tool *uBIQUity* works “behind the scenes”—particularly as an information retrieval system for detecting intertextual references. Unlike other modules that focus on historical, linguistic, or exegetical aspects of the sources, this one is slightly more technical.

Target

Module 4 is designed with humanities scholars in mind, and no prior background in computer science or programming is required.

Lesson Content

Why This Module Exists

The goal of Module 4 is to provide you with a conceptual understanding of:

- How *uBIQUity* retrieves potentially relevant passages
- What retrieval strategies it uses
- Why it combines different approaches
- What the results mean (and do not mean)

Rather than explaining how to “use the interface”, this module explains what the tool is doing when you use it—and why that matters for interpreting its output.

What You Will Learn

Throughout this module, you will be introduced to:

- The basic principles of information retrieval
- Various retrieval strategies, including:
 - Language-agnostic (string-based, trigrams, edit distance)
 - Language-aware (lemmatization, PoS tagging, BM25)
 - Semantic (vector embeddings and similarity)
- The logic of combining multiple strategies
- How to critically evaluate and interpret the results

Each lesson builds on the previous one, moving from general concepts to more specialized methods, followed by practical examples and interpretive reflections.

Our Approach

The module follows a top-down and exploratory approach:

- We begin with foundational ideas, then drill down into specific techniques.
- Concepts are explained qualitatively, with minimal mathematics or programming.
- The aim is not to train you to build retrieval systems, but to help you think critically about how they work—and how they shape your research.

Where relevant, we will include examples from Greek, Latin, and Arabic texts to illustrate each method's impact and limitations. You are encouraged to:

- Take notes on where a method might apply to your own research
- Compare strategies as you go
- Bring a critical eye to the interpretation of system outputs

Module 4.2 – Information Retrieval

Learning Objectives

- Understand the basic goals and functioning of an information retrieval (IR) system
- Recognize the relevance of IR in the study of ancient religious texts
- Situate *uBIQUity* within the broader landscape of IR approaches

Introduction

This lesson introduces the fundamental concepts behind Information Retrieval (IR)—the set of techniques that allow systems to retrieve relevant information from large collections of documents. While originally developed for modern digital libraries and search engines, IR methods are now crucial in the context of digital humanities, where researchers need to locate and interpret textual parallels, echoes, and reuses across vast *corpora*. The goal here is not to turn humanities scholars into computer scientists, but to provide a conceptual map of what IR systems do, and why a tool like *uBIQUity* is built upon them.

Lesson Content

What is Information Retrieval?

Information Retrieval (IR) refers to the process of finding relevant documents or passages within a large dataset, in response to a user query. The query might be a keyword, a sentence, or even an entire paragraph. The system returns a ranked list of items based on their relevance. Unlike database search (which expects exact matches), IR deals with approximate matching, where relevance is a matter of degree. This is particularly useful when:

- The search involves natural language (rather than structured data).
- The match may be inexact (e.g., paraphrased, translated, semantically similar).

Core Concepts of IR Systems

At a high level, most IR systems share a basic structure:

- A corpus: a large collection of documents or texts (e.g., the Bible in Latin and Greek, classical *tafāsīr* in Arabic).
- An indexing component: it transforms the corpus into a searchable structure.
- A retrieval algorithm: it matches the user’s query to the indexed corpus and computes a relevance score.
- A ranking mechanism: it sorts results based on relevance, showing the “most relevant” at the top.

From Web Search to Textual Reuse

In everyday life, we use IR in systems like Google or academic databases. In digital philology or religious textual studies, the problem is different but related: we want to detect whether and how one text reuses another, possibly across time, languages, or genres.

IR allows us to:

- Compare a passage from a patristic commentary with earlier versions of the Bible.
- Trace the reuse of Qur’ānic verses and *Sunnah* in medieval *tafāsīr* literature.
- Identify partial or paraphrased echoes that would be missed by exact search.

This task is especially complex because reuse may involve:

- Synonyms
- Paraphrases
- Translation
- Grammatical variation
- Semantic shifts.

Where *uBIQUity* Fits

uBIQUity is an IR system specifically designed for intertextual search in historical religious *corpora*. It differs from general-purpose search engines in several ways:

- It can operate across multiple languages (Greek, Latin, Arabic).
- It combines classical IR techniques (e.g., string matching) with semantic models (e.g., embeddings).
- It incorporates linguistic features like lemmatization and part-of-speech information when available.

- It supports research workflows, allowing users to save and annotate their findings.

Rather than aiming to find “the right answer,” *uBIQUity* supports exploratory research—surfacing candidate parallels for further human interpretation.

Further Reading

- C.D. Manning, P. Raghavan, and H. Schütze, *Introduction to Information Retrieval*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008: <https://www.math.unipd.it/~aiolli/corsi/0910/IR/irbookprint.pdf>
- M. Hearst, *Search User Interfaces*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009. [Ch.1 for IR basics]

Module 4.3 – Retrieval Strategies and the Hybrid Approach

Learning Objectives

- Understand the variety of strategies used in information retrieval for textual reuse
- Recognize the strengths and limitations of individual strategies (string-based, linguistic, semantic)
- Learn how *uBIQUity* combines multiple approaches to improve the discovery of intertextual references

Introduction

In the previous lesson, we introduced Information Retrieval (IR) as a way of identifying potentially relevant texts in large *corpora*. In this lesson, we dive deeper into how this is done—and why a single strategy is rarely enough. Textual reuse, especially in religious or ancient literature, can be subtle. It may involve exact quotations, reformulations, synonym substitutions, or semantic paraphrases. Relying on one method (e.g., string matching) might miss too much; relying on another (e.g., semantic similarity) might return noise. That is why modern systems like *uBIQUity* use a hybrid retrieval approach: combining different strategies to maximize coverage while maintaining interpretability.

Lesson Content

Types of Retrieval Strategies

At a high level, we can distinguish three main families of strategies:

- String-based (or surface-based): Compare raw character or word sequences (e.g., using edit distance, trigrams).

- Language-aware: Take linguistic features into account—such as lemmatization (normalizing word forms), part-of-speech tags, and stopword removal. This improves results especially for inflected languages.
- Semantic: Use vector representations (embeddings) to capture meaning beyond word forms, enabling detection of paraphrase or conceptual similarity.

Each strategy can return different—and sometimes conflicting—results.

Motivation for a Hybrid Approach

Why not just pick the “best” method? Because each method:

- Works well in certain cases and poorly in others.
- Operates at different levels of abstraction.
- Has different computational costs.

A hybrid approach allows us to:

- Capture both literal and non-literal textual relations.
- Mitigate the weaknesses of individual methods.
- Provide users with multiple signals to interpret relevance.

Score Aggregation and Weighting

In hybrid retrieval systems, different strategies (string-based, linguistic, semantic) each assign a similarity score to a candidate match. To combine these into a single result list, systems often use weighted aggregation—assigning each score a weight based on its importance in the context. For example: Final Score = $0.6 \times \text{string} + 0.3 \times \text{linguistic} + 0.1 \times \text{semantic}$.

Weights can be adjusted depending on the task: higher weight on string similarity for literal reuse, or more emphasis on semantics for paraphrased material. An alternative approach is reranking: each strategy ranks its top results, and a final ranking is built by combining or reshuffling them based on multiple signals. This avoids choosing hard-coded weights and allows more flexibility. Both methods aim to balance precision and recall, and to reflect the complementarity of different retrieval strategies.

Further Reading

- R. Mihalcea, and D. Radev, *Graph-based Natural Language Processing and Information Retrieval*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011.

Module 4.4 – Language Agnostic Search Strategies

Learning Objectives

- Understand what “language-agnostic” means in the context of text retrieval
- Learn how techniques like n-grams and string distance work without relying on linguistic knowledge
- Recognize the strengths and limitations of language-agnostic approaches in intertextual analysis.

Introduction

Some retrieval methods require detailed knowledge of a language’s grammar and vocabulary. Others don’t. In this lesson, we focus on language-agnostic strategies—techniques that work purely on the surface of the text, without needing to know its language, morphology, or syntax. These approaches are particularly valuable when dealing with under-resourced languages, noisy data, or cross-linguistic *corpora*, or simply when linguistic tools (like lemmatizers) are not available or reliable. Despite their simplicity, they can be surprisingly effective in detecting certain kinds of textual reuse.

Lesson Content

What “Language-Agnostic” Means

Language-agnostic strategies operate without any linguistic preprocessing. They treat the text as a raw sequence of characters or tokens and look for patterns, overlaps, or structural similarities. These methods:

- Don’t require part-of-speech tagging or lemmatization
- Work the same way on Latin, Arabic, Greek, or any other language
- Are often computationally efficient and robust to variation.

Common Techniques

- **Token Overlap:** Compare word tokens (without lemmatization). Counts shared tokens, possibly ignoring very common ones (stopwords)
- **n-gram Overlap:** Texts are broken into sequences of n characters or words (e.g., 3-grams = “the”, “he”, “e q”, etc.). Similarity is measured by comparing the number of shared n-grams between query and candidate. This method captures local surface similarity even when exact wording differs slightly

- String Distance Metrics: Measure how different two strings are, character by character. Common examples: Levenshtein distance, Jaccard similarity. Useful for detecting small edits, orthographic variants, or paraphrases.

These techniques are often combined or used as baselines in larger systems.

Strengths and Limitations

Strengths:

- Simple and fast to compute
- Language-independent
- Don't rely on external resources (dictionaries, taggers).

Limitations:

- Can miss semantic or syntactic similarities
- Sensitive to word order and spelling variation
- Less effective when heavy linguistic variation is involved.

Still, in many practical cases—especially when working across languages or with uncertain orthography—these strategies provide a solid foundation for retrieval.

Further Reading

- G. Kondrak, *N-Gram Similarity and Distance*, in *SPIRE'05: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on String Processing and Information Retrieval*, Berlin-Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2005, pp. 115-126.
- G. Navarro, *A Guided Tour to Approximate String Matching*, in “ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)”, 33, 1 (2001), pp. 31-88.

Module 4.5 – Language-Aware Search Strategies

Learning Objectives

- Understand what language-aware search means and how it differs from language-agnostic approaches
- Learn how linguistic preprocessing improves retrieval accuracy
- Recognize the role of lemmatization, part-of-speech tagging, and scoring models like BM25 in retrieval systems.

Introduction

While language-agnostic methods operate at the surface level, language-aware search strategies go deeper—they analyze the structure and meaning of the text using linguistic knowledge. These strategies require tools like lemmatizers, morphological analyzers, or part-of-speech (PoS) taggers, and they are particularly effective for highly inflected or morphologically rich languages, such as Latin, Greek, and Arabic. In this lesson, we explore the main components of language-aware search, and how they enhance the precision and interpretability of information retrieval in intertextual research.

Lesson Content

What Are Language-Aware Strategies?

Language-aware methods use linguistic preprocessing to normalize and enrich the text before it is indexed or compared. Unlike raw string comparison, these methods can:

- Recognize different forms of the same word (e.g., *dixit, dicunt, dico* → *dicere*)
- Tag words by grammatical role (noun, verb, adjective, etc.)
- Filter or weigh stopwords differently based on context.

These techniques allow for more accurate matches across variations in form and syntax.

Lemmatization

Lemmatization reduces words to their dictionary form (lemma). For example:

- Latin: *vidisti, videbit* → *videre*
- Arabic: morphological variations are normalized to root-based lemmas.

This is especially helpful when the same root appears in many inflected forms across texts.

Part-of-Speech (PoS) Tagging

PoS tagging assigns grammatical categories (e.g., noun, verb, preposition) to each word. This information can be used to:

- Improve disambiguation (e.g., *mens* as noun vs. verb)
- Prioritize content-bearing words over function words in scoring

While not always perfect, PoS tagging can make retrieval more precise, especially in long or ambiguous queries.

Scoring with BM25

BM25 is a standard scoring algorithm in IR, which takes into account:

- Term frequency: how often a term appears in a document
- Inverse document frequency: how rare the term is across the corpus
- Document length normalization.

When combined with lemmatized and tagged data, BM25 provides a more nuanced relevance score than raw overlap or string similarity.

Further Reading

- C. Manning and H. Schütze, *Foundations of Statistical Natural Language Processing*, Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1999.
- S. Robertson and H. Zaragoza, *The Probabilistic Relevance Framework: BM25 and Beyond*, in “Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval”, 3, 4 (2009), pp. 333-389.

Module 4.6 – Semantic Search and Vector Embedding

Learning Objectives

- Understand the concept of semantic similarity and how it differs from string-based matching
- Learn the basics of vector representations (embeddings) in information retrieval
- Recognize how semantic search can support the identification of intertextual relationships.

Introduction

In previous lessons, we explored how string-based and language-aware methods retrieve texts based on form, grammar, or structure. But what if a passage rephrases a concept entirely, or uses different words to express the same idea? This is where semantic search becomes essential. It allows retrieval systems to match texts based on meaning rather than surface form. This lesson introduces the idea of vector embeddings, a mathematical way of representing word and sentence meaning, and explains how they are used in modern information retrieval systems to support conceptual similarity detection.

Lesson Content

What Is Semantic Search?

Semantic search aims to go beyond literal matches by retrieving results that are conceptually similar to the query—even if they use different words or phrasing.

For example:

- Query: “God is merciful”
- Match: “The Lord shows compassion”.

This kind of match is difficult (or impossible) for string-based methods but can be captured through semantic techniques.

What Are Embeddings?

An embedding is a way to represent a word, sentence, or document as a vector—a list of numbers—in a high-dimensional space. The key idea is that similar meanings are located near each other in this space. There are several kinds of embeddings:

- Word embeddings: Each word has its own vector (e.g., Word2Vec, GloVe)
- Sentence embeddings: Entire sentences are encoded as single vectors (e.g., Sentence-BERT, LASER)
- Contextual embeddings: Vectors depend on the surrounding words (e.g., BERT, mBERT).

Similarity between vectors is usually computed using cosine similarity, which measures how “close” two vectors are in direction.

Semantic Search in Practice

In a retrieval system:

- Both the query and the candidate texts are embedded.
- The system computes a semantic similarity score between vectors.
- Results are ranked based on this score.

This approach:

- Enables cross-lingual retrieval when using multilingual embeddings
- Detects conceptual overlap, even with paraphrased or loosely related texts
- Complements string-based methods, especially in noisy or flexible textual traditions.

Trade-offs and Challenges

Advantages:

- This approach captures paraphrase, synonymy, and broader semantic relations
- It supports retrieval across translation boundaries
- It does not rely on exact vocabulary.

Challenges:

- Embeddings may be opaque (hard to interpret)
- Performance depends on training data and model quality
- This approach may retrieve semantically plausible but irrelevant results.

In intertextual research, semantic search provides a powerful exploratory tool, but its results often require human judgment and critical interpretation.

Further Reading

- T. Mikolov, K. Chen, G. Corrado, and J. Dean, *Efficient Estimation of Word Representations in Vector Space*, in *1st International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2013 (Scottsdale, Arizona, USA, May 2-4, 2013), Workshop Track Proceedings*, 2013: arXiv preprint arXiv:1301.3781.
- N. Reimers and I. Gurevych, *Sentence-BERT: Sentence Embeddings Using Siamese BERT-Networks*, in *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing and the 9th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (EMNLP-IJCNLP)*, 2019, pp. 3982-3992: arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.10084.
- J. Devlin, M.W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, *BERT: Pre-Training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding*, in *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, vol. 1, 2019, pp. 4171-4186.

Module 4.7 – Putting It All Together

Learning Objectives

- Understand how different retrieval strategies work together in a realistic workflow
- See how multiple similarity signals (string, linguistic, semantic) complement one another
- Recognize the practical challenges of interpreting results in intertextual search.

Introduction

After exploring string-based, language-aware, and semantic search strategies separately, it's time to see how they come together in a real-world retrieval task. This lesson walks through a simplified example of how multiple retrieval signals are combined to detect candidate instances of textual reuse. Rather than focusing on implementation details, our goal here is to show how the logic of the retrieval process flows, and how results can be interpreted critically by the human user.

Lesson Content

The Scenario

Imagine we are analyzing a passage from a late antique commentary and suspect it may reuse a verse or passage from the *Vulgate* Bible. The researcher submits a short query (a few verses or phrases) to the retrieval system. The system runs multiple strategies in parallel, each returning a list of potential matches:

- String-based comparison yields several near-verbatim hits
- Language-aware search reveals additional candidates with shared lemmatized terms and similar syntactic structures
- Semantic search surfaces conceptually related passages—some paraphrased, some using different vocabulary entirely.

Each candidate passage is scored independently by each strategy.

Making Sense of the Results

The proposed example illustrates the complementarity of the three approaches:

- String similarity is reliable for exact reuse but brittle when form changes
- Linguistic similarity helps bridge inflectional and syntactic variation
- Semantic similarity identifies deeper connections but is harder to interpret.

A hybrid approach provides multiple perspectives, and ultimately, the researcher decides which results are meaningful.

Human-in-the-Loop

This workflow emphasizes the importance of the human user:

- Not all high scores are meaningful
- Not all low scores are irrelevant

- Context, genre, and scholarly intent matter.

The retrieval system offers candidates, not conclusions. Its power lies in surfacing possibilities for further investigation.

Further Reading

- M.L. Jockers, *Macroanalysis: Digital Methods and Literary History*, Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 2013.
- M. Büchler, A. Geßner, M. Berti, and T. Eckart, *Measuring the Influence of a Work by Text Re-use*, in S. Dunn and S. Mahony (eds.), *The Digital Classicist 2013*, London: Institute of Classical Studies, 2013, pp. 63-79.

Module 4.8 – Measuring the Performance of a Retrieval System

Learning Objectives

- Understand how retrieval systems are evaluated for effectiveness
- Learn key metrics used to assess ranked results (e.g., MRR, precision, recall)
- Recognize the limitations of automatic evaluation in the context of intertextual search.

Introduction

How do we know whether a retrieval system is doing a good job? In this lesson, we introduce some of the standard metrics used to evaluate the performance of retrieval systems. These metrics come from the field of information retrieval evaluation, where systems are judged based on their ability to return relevant documents at the top of the results list. While these metrics are useful, especially during system development and tuning, they have limitations—particularly in fields like intertextual research, where relevance is often subjective and context-dependent.

Lesson Content

Relevance and Ranking

Retrieval systems do more than find matches—they rank them. Ideally, the most relevant result should appear first, followed by others in descending order of relevance. But what does “relevant” mean? In most evaluation settings:

- A gold standard set of known correct matches is used
- The system’s output is compared against this standard

- The position of relevant results in the list affects the evaluation score.

Key Metrics

Precision and Recall

- Precision: What percentage of retrieved results are relevant?
 $\text{Precision} = (\text{relevant retrieved}) / (\text{total retrieved})$
- Recall: What percentage of all relevant results were retrieved?
 $\text{Recall} = (\text{relevant retrieved}) / (\text{total relevant})$.

High precision means few false positives, while high recall means few false negatives. Often, we seek a balance between the two.

MRR (Mean Reciprocal Rank):

- Measures how early the first correct result appears in the list.
- Formula: $\text{MRR} = \text{average of } (1 / \text{rank of first relevant result}) \text{ across queries}$.
- A higher MRR means relevant results tend to appear closer to the top.

Evaluation in Intertextual Search

In more controlled domains (like web search or legal text retrieval), evaluation can be automatic. In intertextual studies, however:

- “Relevance” may be interpretive, not absolute
- Different scholars may disagree on what counts as a reuse
- Results may be useful even if not “correct” in a strict sense.

Because of this, quantitative evaluation must often be complemented by qualitative analysis and user validation. Still, performance metrics are valuable for:

- Comparing algorithms
- Tuning system parameters
- Measuring improvement over time.

Further Reading

- C.D. Manning, P. Raghavan, and H. Schütze, *Introduction to Information Retrieval*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008: <https://www.math.unipd.it/~aiolli/corsi/0910/IR/irbookprint.pdf>
- E.M. Voorhees and D.K. Harman (eds.), *TREC: Experiment and Evaluation in Information Retrieval*, Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2005.
- T.Y. Liu, *Learning to Rank for Information Retrieval*, in “Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval”, 3, 3 (2009), pp. 225-331.

Module 4.9 – Making Sense of the Data

Learning Objectives

- Develop a critical understanding of retrieval results and their limitations
- Reflect on the role of interpretation in evaluating candidate matches
- Understand the difference between retrieval assistance and automated decision-making.

Introduction

At this point, we have explored how information retrieval systems work, what strategies they use, and how we measure their performance. But now comes the most important part—making sense of the results. This lesson is not about algorithms, but about you, the researcher. The system might retrieve high-scoring matches—but are they meaningful? Can you trust them? What do they actually say about intertextuality? Here, we take a step back and reflect on how to interpret retrieval data responsibly and productively.

Lesson Content

Retrieval Is Not Interpretation

A system might return a passage with:

- High string similarity—but no real reuse
- High semantic similarity—but only vague thematic connection
- Medium scores—but subtle, meaningful echoes that scores didn’t fully capture.

In other words: relevance is not binary, and scores are not judgments. They are clues, not conclusions.

Heuristics for Interpreting Results

As a researcher, you might ask:

- Does this candidate fit the historical or theological context of reuse?
- Is there a rhetorical or polemical reason for paraphrasing the original?
- Does the pattern appear across multiple texts, or is it isolated?
- Are there multiple weak signals (low string but high semantic and linguistic) that together justify closer attention?

Retrieval systems cannot answer these questions—but they can help you ask them.

Limits of the System

IR systems, including hybrid ones, have important limitations:

- Bias in the *corpora* or embeddings can affect results
- Spurious matches are always possible, especially with short queries
- Noise can arise from OCR errors, editorial choices, or inconsistent markup.

Even “perfect” algorithms do not replace close reading, historical awareness, or critical judgment.

A New Kind of Research Process

The real power of these tools is not in automating research—but in augmenting it:

- You explore, filter, and interpret
- The system expands your perceptual field, surfacing candidates you might not have thought to look for
- You decide what counts as reuse, echo, influence, or coincidence.

This is the core of human-in-the-loop intertextuality: not mechanical detection, but collaborative discovery.

Further Reading

- G. Rockwell and S. Sinclair, *Hermeneutica: Computer-Assisted Interpretation in the Humanities*, Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2016.
- P. Molitor and J. Ritter, *Digital Methods for Intertextuality Studies*, in “it-Information Technology”, 62, 2 (2020), pp. 49-51.

Module 5 – Comparative and Semantic Digital Analysis. Introduction to the Use of the *uBIQUity* Tool Developed by the Research Group. Case Studies: Greek, Latin, and Arabic

Introduction

This module introduces the practical use of the *uBIQUity* tool for comparative and semantic digital analysis. It provides a step-by-step walkthrough of the platform’s main features, illustrating how users can perform searches, apply filters, and analyze intertextual relationships across the Greek, Latin, and Arabic datasets. Through a series of guided examples and screenshots, the module demonstrates how to navigate the interface, interpret search results, and compare texts using the different visualization modes available in *uBIQUity*—from Parallel View and Variant Graph to Node-Based and Distant Reading views. The session also explains how to create, save, and manage research flows, add personal notes and bibliographic references, and export data for further analysis. By the end of the module, users will have a clear understanding of how to explore and interpret textual connections within a large multilingual corpus using *uBIQUity* platform.

Learning Objectives

By the end of this module, students will be able to:

- Navigate the *uBIQUity* interface and understand its main functional areas
- Perform searches across Arabic, Greek, and Latin datasets using different comparison criteria and filters
- Interpret and organize search results through the tool’s various visualization modes
- Use metadata, chronological, and geographical filters to refine intertextual analysis
- Create, annotate, and manage personalized research flows
- Export and document results for further study or collaborative use.

Target

Students and researchers in the humanities who wish to learn how to use the *uBIQUity* tool and perform practical searches and analyses within its digital environment.

Lesson Content

This module introduces the practical use of the *uBIQUity* tool for comparative and semantic digital analysis. It guides users through the main functions of the interface—from performing searches and applying filters to comparing results and managing research flows across the Greek, Latin, and Arabic datasets. The next section describes the basic workflow of the *uBIQUity* interface, focusing on search initiation and filter selection.

First, the user (logged in or not logged in) who wishes to start a search within the *uBIQUity* tool selects the reference language by choosing among Arabic, Greek, and Latin, located at the top left of the main screen. They select a language and type one or more words into the Search Text box.

The screenshot shows the ITSERR search interface. At the top left is the ITSERR logo with the text 'Associated project to RESILIENCE'. Below the logo is a navigation bar with 'Home / Flow'. Underneath is a language selection menu with 'Arabic', 'Greek', and 'Latin' (which is underlined). Below the menu is a search text box containing the placeholder text 'ex.' and the example text 'Terra autem erat inanis et vacua'.

The user sees on the left side of the main search screen a section dedicated to the selection of filters, allowing them to guide and refine the search.

The filters available for the Arabic language, selectable by the user, are the following:

- Comparison Criteria (Exact, Inflections, Roots, Synonyms, Structures)
- Sources and Authors, further divided into:
 - Qur'ān → with the option to select one or more chapters (Select chapters)
 - Authors → to filter between *Ḥadīth*, *Sīrah*, *Tafsīr* and related authors (Author name) and books (Books)
- Geography → It displays a map to select the region of interest
- Chronology → It shows a slider to select the period expressed in centuries, as well as the indication of years (From Year – To Year).

The screenshot shows the ITSERR web application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the ITSERR logo and the text 'Associated project to RESILIENCE'. Below this, there is a breadcrumb trail 'Home / Flow'. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Language Selection:** 'Arabic', 'Greek', and 'Latin' tabs are visible, with 'Arabic' currently selected.
- Search Input:** A text input field containing Arabic text: '١ الْحَمْدُ لِلَّهِ رَبِّ الْعَالَمِينَ ٢ الْقُرْآنُ الْمَجِيدُ ٣ مَلِكُ الْكَوْكَبِينَ'. To the right of the input is a '.ex' label.
- Comparison Criteria:** A section with a search icon, containing buttons for 'Exact', 'Inflections', 'Roots', and 'Synonyms'. The 'Exact' button is highlighted. Below these is a '+ Structures' button.
- Sources & Authors:** A section with a dropdown arrow, containing:
 - Qur'an
Select chapters
 - Authors
 - Ḥadīth
 - Sirah
 - Tafsīr
 - Author name (dropdown menu)
 - Books (dropdown menu)
- Geography:** A section with a map icon.
- Chronology:** A section with a calendar icon.

At the bottom of the interface, there are two buttons: 'Reset' and 'Search'.

The filters available for the Latin and Greek languages, selectable by the user, are the following:

- Comparison Criteria (Exact, Inflections, Roots, Synonyms, Structures)
- Compare (To Text, To Text & Apparatus)
- Scriptures and Authors, further divided into:
 - Scriptures → to filter one or more versions of the Bible and related books (Select books)
 - Ancient Authors → to filter one or more authors (Author name) and one or more work titles (Work title)
- Geography → It displays a map to select the region of interest
- Chronology → It shows a slider to select the period expressed in centuries, as well as the indication of years (From Year – To Year).

The screenshot shows the ITSERR search interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home / Flow' and language tabs for 'Arabic', 'Greek', and 'Latin'. Below this is a search input field containing the text 'Terra autem erat inanis et vacua'. Underneath the search field are 'Comparison criteria' tabs: 'Exact', 'Inflections', 'Roots', 'Synonyms', and 'Structures'. Below the tabs is a 'Compare' section with radio buttons for 'To Text' (selected) and 'To Text & Apparatus'. The 'Scriptures & Authors' section is expanded, showing checkboxes for 'Scriptures' and 'Ancient Authors'. Under 'Scriptures', there are four options: 'B.VL - Beuron (ed.), Vetus Latina', 'S.VL - Sabatier (ed.), Vetus Latina', 'W.VULG - Weber-Gryson (ed.), Vulgate', and 'W_all - Weber-Gryson (ed.), Vulgate (Alternative Text)'. Under 'Ancient Authors', there are two dropdown menus for 'Author name' and 'Work title'. At the bottom, there are sections for 'Geography' and 'Chronology'.

Once the search has started, by clicking on the Search button, the user sees the list of obtained search results. From the list of results, the user can sort the results using the Sort By filter and selecting one of the following options:

- Similarity → considering the result with the highest similarity score obtained, in the case of Structures search
- Author (A–Z) → considering alphabetical order
- Chronology → considering chronological order.

The screenshot shows a 'Sort by' dropdown menu. The menu is open, showing three options: 'Similarity', 'Author (A-Z)', and 'Chronology'. The 'Similarity' option is currently selected and highlighted in blue. Above the dropdown menu, there is a 'New Search' button and three icons: an upload arrow, a download arrow, and a settings gear.

Only in the case of a multi-word search, the user receives for each result an indication of the Matching Word Count (in blue), which corresponds to the number of matches between the individual result and the searched text.

T **2/2** Fons autem adscendebat de terra, et irrigabat omnem faciem terrae.

In addition, in the specific case of a search by Structures comparison criterion, the system also displays the Similarity Score. A higher score for each result indicates to the user a higher level of similarity with the searched word or text.

T **1/2** Planxit terra, corruptus est orbis terrae, planxerunt alti terrae.

Similarity Score 0.89

From the obtained results, the user can click on the result title to read the full text, displayed in Browsing mode, with the reference verse highlighted in yellow. From here, the user can also view the complete apparatus, if available, by activating the Apparatus switch at the top.

ITSERR
Associated project to RESILIENCE

Home / Flow

1. Search (10) X Svl_genesis 13 X

Svl_genesis 13:6 Apparatus

Text
2/2

13.1 Et ascendit Abram ex Aegypto, ipse et uxor eius, et omnia quae illius erant, et Loth cum eo, in desertum.

13.2 Erat autem Abram dives valde in pecore, et argento, et auro.

13.3 Et abiit unde venerat in desertum, usque Bethel, ad locum ubi fuerat tabernaculum eius prius, inter Bethel et inter Agge,

13.4 in locum ubi altare fecerat initio, et invocaverat ibi Abram nomen Dei.

13.5 Et Lot qui simul ambulabat cum Abram, erant oves, et boves, et tabernacula.

13.6 **Et non capiebat illos terra, habitare simul ...**

The user, always from the list of results, can choose the comparison mode in addition to the consultation mode of the chapter. The user can therefore select one, two, or three results simultaneously and start the comparison by clicking on the Compare Selected button.

The comparison mode of results allows the user, both in the case of a single-word search and a multi-word search, to compare texts through different visualization modes, which are:

- Parallel View → It shows the user as many columns as compared results, in addition to the Searched Text column, and, if available, the apparatus.

- Variant Graph → It shows the user the graph of variant readings for each individual result in the case of results with an apparatus to compare.

The user (logged in) can add personal Notes by clicking the note icon on each result, on graph nodes, or by selecting part of the text, both in Browsing and Searching mode, filling in at least the mandatory fields before saving. In the same section, the user also has access to external resources by clicking the Bibliographic Reference field and the related Zotero icon.

The user (logged in) can also insert general notes in the dedicated section accessible via the Notes button.

Once operations on the flow are complete, the user (logged in) proceeds with saving it by clicking the Create Flow button, enabled once at least one result comparison is generated. The user (logged in) fills in the mandatory Flow name field and views a summary of the performed navigation. The flow saved by the user (logged in) is made visible in the dedicated Flows section, which will contain the list of all saved flows.

By clicking on Flows and then on the *Run uBIQUity* button, the user (logged in) can load a saved flow related to a previous search. In the same Flows section, users also have access to actions such as retrieving previous versions of the same Flow (hourglass icon), editing the saved flow (pencil icon), and deleting a flow (trash icon), the latter not clickable if it is the current flow.

A user with a dedicated role can provide feedback on a specific result by giving positive or negative evaluations for a specific searched text and selected filters, in order to influence the model. By clicking the thumbs up and/or thumbs down icon, filling in the mandatory field, and finally saving by

clicking Save, confirmation is shown that a positive and/or negative rating has been given on the specific result. The section called *See ratings* allows logged-in users to view detailed information on released ratings.

In the case of a single-word search, the user (logged in or not logged in) has access to additional visualization modes, which are:

- Word Frequency → It shows the graph of occurrences of a word over time, considering the author’s chronology and calculated across the entire corpus of the selected language.

Dictionary → It shows a dictionary entry of the single term with details regarding Lemma, Morphology, and Definition. The user (logged in or not logged in) can also view the same dictionary by selecting any word in the text and clicking the (i) icon.

By clicking one of the top tabs in the main screen, available for each language (see images below), the user can access Browsing mode for a more complete reading of the entire corpus. In this mode, the user can use the available filters, which vary depending on the selected language and reference source, following the same structure outlined above for Searching mode, and in some cases also filtering by Chapter and Verse.

Arabic Corpus

Browse corpus chapters.

Greek Corpus

Browse corpus chapters.

Latin Corpus

Browse corpus chapters.

The user can export a JSON file containing information related to the performed search flow by clicking on the icon highlighted below (in red).

Module 6 – Visualization Systems: Close Reading and Distant Reading; A Node-based UI to Build and Share Knowledge

Learning Objectives

- Understand the concepts of close and distant reading
- See how both approaches contribute to discovering intertextual references
- Learn how node-based interfaces support
- Enhance this discovery process.

Introduction

This module explores the complementary methods of close and distant reading to analyze intertextual relationships across texts. Students will learn to interpret literary references through detailed textual analysis and digital tools, with a focus on *uBIQUnity* node-based interfaces for visualizing textual networks. Participants will develop critical and digital literacy skills for discovering and mapping intertextuality using the *uBIQUnity* tool (also with hands-on activities and Moodle-based interactions in the platform).

Target

This module is intended for scholars in philology, religious studies, and the digital humanities, as well as visual communication and data visualization designers, and anyone broadly interested in exploring these intersections.

Lesson Content

What Is Close Reading?

- Close reading is a detailed, line-by-line analysis of a text
- It focuses on language, style, structure, and rhetorical devices
- It allows readers to explore nuances, ambiguities, and cultural context.

What Is Distant Reading?

- Coined by Franco Moretti, distant reading is data-driven analysis of large textual *corpora*
- It involves computational tools to observe trends, patterns, or networks over many texts
- You do not read individual texts; instead, you read metadata, frequencies, or relationships.

Why Both Matter?

Close reading gives us depth. Distant reading gives us breadth.

- Close reading helps us understand the original context of a text and how it is reused
- Distant reading shows us where it recurs, how frequently, and in what genres or historical periods.

What Is Intertextuality?

Intertextuality is the relationship between texts—how one text refers to or is shaped by another. According to Davide Dainese and Anna Mambelli (2024, see *Further Reading*): “Intertextuality shows that every text is a node in an infinite network of cultural references, making reading a dynamic and stratified process.”

Where *uBIQUity* Fits

To explore intertextuality, researchers typically follow a structured workflow:

1. They begin by querying a textual passage using one or more comparison criteria—such as exact match, inflections, roots, synonyms, antonyms, or structural-AI analysis
2. They then review and sort the resulting list of sentence similarity matches
3. They select two or more relevant results for closer comparison
4. They initiate a detailed comparison of the selected texts.

At this point, the system automatically generates branches corresponding to the number of selected texts. Each branch divides into two sub-branches: one displays the results of text-to-text comparisons, and the other shows comparisons between the text and its critical apparatus (if available). If the edition lacks a critical apparatus—due to copyright restrictions or editorial absence—the second sub-branch is omitted.

The comparison process yields a relevance or “fusion” rate, offering a guided pathway that can be interpreted in two modes: distant reading and close reading. In distant reading mode, researchers see the quantity and distribution of intertextual references between texts via interactive maps. Clicking on any node within a map reveals the passage in its broader textual context. These visual and quantitative insights direct the researcher toward specific areas of interest, which can then be explored more deeply using two close reading modes:

- Parallel comparison, which presents multiple texts side by side for line-by-line analysis of variants—resembling the traditional method of laying books open on a table
- Variant graph, particularly useful for embracing the “granularity” of each of the texts under comparison. Indeed, it shows the variant readings related to each textual passage obtained as a result of the research.

Tools like *TRAViz* (*Text Re-use Alignment Visualization*) enhance this process by aligning individual tokens across different versions and displaying them in a subway-map style. This makes it easier to trace the textual paths, variations, and alignments across ancient and modern editions.

In addition to comparing whole passages, the researcher can zoom into a single term using computational linguistic tools—such as frequency graphs or word clouds—embedded within each node via an API (*Application Programming Interface*). These tools enable new investigative paths, branching off from the initial research thread and forming complex workflows.

From the search view, users can initiate a new query—either in parallel with the first (using different criteria like synonyms or roots), or by modifying the original query. All actions are recorded in a dynamic, node-based interface. Notes can be attached at both the workflow and individual operation levels, with fields for textual commentary and bibliographic references. These notes can be retrieved, listed, and shared, providing a powerful system for documenting and managing the researcher’s analytical process.

In conclusion, *uBIQUity* is a significant advancement in the field of digital humanities and beyond, providing an innovative software for researching intertextual references between sacred texts and ancient Christian and Islamic exegetical works. The transdisciplinary approach, along with the integration of AI and human expertise, allows for enhanced precision and flexibility in research.

Further Reading

- D. Dainese and A. Mambelli, *Intertestualità tra Bibbie e antichi commentari cristiani: l'esempio di simul nel De Genesi ad litteram di Agostino*, in “Lexicon Philosophicum: International Journal for the History of Texts and Ideas”, 11 (2023–2024), pp. 39-65. Open access: <https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/article/view/872/726>
- F. D’Avenia, C. Ferrara, C. Palillo, and M. Costa, *Ubiquity. Il design della comunicazione nel progetto ITSERR*, in G. Di Bucchianico and A. Marano (eds.), *Design per la diversità*, Pescara: Società Italiana di Design, 2024, pp. 369-377.
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- F. Moretti, *A una certa distanza. Leggere i testi letterari nel nuovo millennio*, Roma: Carocci, 2020.
- F. Moretti, *Falso movimento. La svolta quantitativa nello studio della letteratura*. Milano: Nottetempo, 2022.
- C. Palillo and M. Costa, *Information Design and Data Visualization in the ITSERR Project*, in *P/References of Design. Cumulus Conference Proceedings Budapest 2024*, vol. 1, Budapest: Cumulus Association, 2024, pp. 2525-2532: <https://doi.org/10.63442/QKLZ5498>
- C. Palillo, C. Ferrara, D. Savasta, and M. Costa, *From Data to Interpretation: Designing Modular Visualizations for Capta in Digital Humanities*, in D. Hasırcı, G. Mura, E. Yıldız, A.R. Bayrak (eds.), *Failing (Well) in Design Writing*, Izmir: Izmir University of Economics Press, 2025, pp. 124-129.

4. PUBLICATIONS

Publications authored by some members of the WP8 team and related to this specific deliverable (D8.2) are listed below:

- L. Bigoni, D. Dainese, and A. Mambelli, *uBIQUity and Resilient Septuagint: Transdisciplinary and Interrelated Research Projects on Sacred Texts and their Receptions*, in “Journal of Septuagint and Cognate Studies”, 57 (2024), pp. 271-272.
- C. Palillo and M. Costa, *Information Design and Data Visualization in the ITSERR Project*, in *P/References of Design. Cumulus Conference Proceedings Budapest 2024*, vol. 1, Budapest: Cumulus Association, 2024, pp. 2525-2532: <https://doi.org/10.63442/QKLZ5498>
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